

HUMAN-CENTRIC AI-ENABLED EXTENDED REALITY APPLICATIONS FOR THE
INDUSTRY 5.0 ERA

D3.1– HUMAN-CENTRIC DIGITAL TWIN DESIGN AND
IMPLEMENTATION

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Definition
AAS	asset administration shell
AMR	autonomous mobile robot
AMT	aircraft maintenance technician
ANOVA	analysis of variance
ANS	autonomic nervous system
API	application programming interface
AR	augmented reality
BPM	beats per minute
BLE	bluetooth low energy
COBOT	collaborative robot
DT	digital twin
EDA	electrodermal activity
GUI	graphical user interface
HDT	human-centric digital twin
HDM	historical data manager
HF	high frequency
HR	heart rate
HRV	heart rate variability
JSON	javascript object notation
KPI	key performance indicator
LAN	local area network
LF	low frequency
ML	machine learning
MoCap	motion capture
MQTT	message queuing telemetry transport
MR	mixed reality
MSD	musculoskeletal disorders
NASA-TLX	NASA task load index
OPC-UA	open platform communications – unified architecture
REST	representational state transfer
RMSSD	means root mean square of successive differences
SAS	stress analog scale
SCL	skin conductance level
SCR	skin conductance response
SPL	sound pressure level
SSQ	simulator sickness questionnaire
UXQ	user experience questionnaire
VR	virtual reality
XR	extended reality

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The document outlines the development of Human-centric Digital Twins within the XR5.0 project, emphasizing the integration of human factors into Industry 5.0 applications using Extended Reality. The report includes the work done in three different tasks (T3.1, T3.2 and T3.3) under the WP3.

The document makes the foundation for the extension, use and integration of Clawdite, the IIoT platform dedicated to the creation of Human-centric Digital Twins in XR5.0. The document reports an extensive literature review on human-centric digital twins in manufacturing.

Building on this review, it examines relevant human factors and models for XR5.0, with a particular emphasis on mental stress. It defines key stress indicators, including physiological (heart rate, EDA), behavioral (eye tracking, pupil dilation), and self-reported (workload questionnaires). The proposed framework ensures adaptive system responses to optimize human performance and well-being in XR applications.

Additionally, the document outlines components for data collection and communication, supporting the development of Human-centric Digital Twins. It details data acquisition from workers (wearable sensors, eye trackers) and machines (Asset Administration Shells). Furthermore, it presents the design and implementation of HDTs within the Clawdite platform, describing the architecture, functional modules, and interoperability mechanisms that enable scalable and adaptable digital twins.

The main results from T3.1, T3.2 and T3.3 in this first period include:

- Extensive literature review about Human-centric Digital Twins and XR applications
- A framework for assessing human factors, in particular mental stress, in XR environments
- A framework for collecting, processing, and analyzing personal data from both human and machine dimensions to enhance Human-centric Digital Twins
- Enhancement of Clawdite
 - Clawdite docs + examples and walkthrough (<https://clawdite.spslab.ch/docs/>)
 - Clawdite instance dedicated to XR5.0 (3 partners involved)
 - Platform improvements and bug fixing
- Development of the Functional Module “Worker Movement Prediction”
 - Multiple human detection through AI deep models (YOLO)
 - Experiments with different prediction models
 - Interface for displaying worker detection and movements prediction
- Conception of the Functional Module “Worker Shadowing”
 - Prototype for tracking head and hands movements through the visor
- Connectors for Google Fit and NovAAS
- Two papers published:
 - HFR 2024: “Improving Collaborative Robotics: Insights On The Impact of Human Intention Prediction”
 - APMS 2024: “Impact of Collaborative Robots on Human Trust, Anxiety, and Workload: Experiment Findings”

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Objectives of the Deliverable

The work performed in this deliverable (D3.1 - Human-Centric Digital Twin Design and Implementation) reports the activities and results conducted in Task 3.1 - Worker Digital Image Modelling and Specifications, led by IPIA, Task 3.2 - Personal Data Collection and Analytics, led by UNP, Task 3.3 - Human Centric Digital Twins, led by SUPSI.

The deliverable aims to provide a detailed overview of XR5.0's human-centric digital twins (HDTs) by focusing on their design, implementation, and integration into Industry 5.0 applications. It aims to highlight how HDTs enhance the synergy between humans and technology in manufacturing processes, with a particular focus on extended reality (XR) environments central to XR5.0. The objectives of the deliverable are as follows:

- **Design and implement HDT models** that accurately represent the unique traits, behaviours, and contexts of workers. These models will include a comprehensive specification for the collection and modelling of worker characteristics, ensuring compliance with regulatory frameworks such as GDPR and ethical considerations. The design will emphasize creating a foundation for personalized and human-centric digital interactions within XR environments. The work, discussed in Chapter 3, is part of Task 3.1 (**IPIA**).
- **Develop robust components** to support effective data collection for HDT creation, integrating APIs and modular layers to gather data from a diverse range of physical and digital sources. This will facilitate seamless aggregation and management of multimodal data, enhancing the accuracy and adaptability of the HDT platform. The work, discussed in Chapter 4, is part of Task 3.2 (**UNP**).
- **Establish a system for efficient HDT creation** that provides XR5.0 solution providers with a streamlined and scalable mechanism for generating HDTs. This system will leverage advanced insights from sensors, functional modules, and personal data analytics to enable real-time data processing and seamless integration with XR environments. Utilizing SUPSI's Clawdite platform as a foundation, the system will deliver highly realistic digital representations tailored for personalized XR functionalities. The work, discussed in Chapter 5, is part of Task 3.3 (**SUPSI**).
- **Develop functional modules that enrich HDTs** with data-driven insights and advanced predictive capabilities. By incorporating complex features derived from functional modules, the models will integrate estimated, predicted, and simulated traits, creating dynamic and adaptive digital twins. These functional enhancements will enable more realistic, responsive, and personalized worker representations for enhanced interaction in XR environments. Also in this case, the work, discussed in especially in Chapter 5.3, is part of Task 3.3 (**SUPSI**).

1.2 Insights from Other Tasks and Deliverables

Results reported in D3.1 and activities performed in the related tasks relying on:

- **D1.4 – Ethical Management and Regulatory Compliance Framework:** it provides ethical and legal requirements for AI and XR systems, including GDPR compliance, data protection, and cybersecurity considerations. It is relevant to D3.1 for defining the Framework for Personal Data Collection and Analytics, ensuring worker digital twins respect data privacy regulations and ethical AI use.
- **D2.1 – Requirements and Reference Scenarios Analysis:** it defines six pilot projects and reference scenarios, including (H)DTs applications, immersive training, remote assistance, and AI-driven personalization. Useful for D3.1 in identifying use cases for HDTs in the XR5.0 Project and modelling worker digital images.
- **D2.2 – Reference Architecture Model and Technical Specifications:** it describes the technical architecture for XR5.0, including AI models, APIs, and integration frameworks. Directly applicable

to D3.1 in defining “Design and Implementation of Human-centric Digital Twins”, ensuring compatibility with the Clawdite platform.

- **D6.1 – Use Cases Co-Creation and Pilot Sites Preparation:** it details co-creation workshops that define key user needs, human factors, and performance metrics for Industry 5.0 applications. It supports the definition of the Modelling and Specifications of Worker Digital Images, ensuring alignment with real-world industry needs.

1.3 Structure

This document is structured in 6 chapters. **Chapter 1** outlines the objectives of the deliverable, its relation to the broader XR5.0 project, and the integration of HDTs and human-centred paradigm in the XR5.0 solutions. **Chapter 2** introduces the concept of HDTs, their role in Industry 5.0, and how they enhance worker integration, ergonomics, and real-time decision-making, with particular reference to the XR5.0 domain. **Chapter 3** presents a structured framework for assessing physiological, behavioral, and self-reported data to enhance worker well-being, for the human factors integration into XR environments. **Chapter 4** details the methods for collecting, processing, and analyzing personal data to improve the accuracy and responsiveness of HDTs. **Chapter 5** describes the conceptual design, architecture, and functional modules of the Clawdite platform, as well as the Functional Modules developed in T3.3. And finally, **Chapter 6** summarizes key findings, highlights achievements, and outlines future directions for the continued development of human-centric digital twins.

1.4 Relation with the XR5.0 Architecture

WP3 leverages the Clawdite platform as the central integration hub, ensuring data aggregation and interoperability across various components of the XR5.0 ecosystem. As the single source of truth for worker-related data, Clawdite facilitates the collection, structuring, and management of dynamic and static data, encompassing not only worker-specific information but also from the environment, industrial assets, and XR devices.

As illustrated in **Error! Reference source not found.**, the **modelling specifications and guidelines** for worker-related aspects are established in T3.1, which defines the structure and methodology for worker data representation. These specifications are further complemented by **worker data collection methods and analytics** solutions developed in T3.2, ensuring robust mechanisms for capturing and processing relevant human-centric data.

The development of **Functional Modules**, alongside the **Clawdite platform**, takes place within T3.3. These modules serve as **enhancements** to HDTs, enriching them with **real-time and predictive data insights**, complementing T3.2’s data collection methods. Data collected inside Clawdite Core Infrastructure (i.e., characteristics, measurements and states) constitutes the input of Functional Modules. The output from such modules (i.e., states) in turn feeds the Platform, which forwards it to the components that need it: namely the **Pilots**, T3.4 for creating **personalized training programs**, and T3.5, which designs and integrates **adaptive algorithms**, embedded as Functional Modules themselves. These algorithms enable the XR’s and traditional GUIs to dynamically and personalise interface experiences in alignment with the XR5.0 framework.

A **structured and unified approach to data modelling and integration pipelines** ensures consistency across WP3 while maintaining interoperability with other work packages. This approach enhances the **scalability** and **flexibility** of the XR5.0 architecture, fostering smooth interaction between industrial assets, XR interfaces, and worker models.

Finally, **training programs**, which incorporate the adaptive algorithms developed in T3.5, are built upon **user data stored within Clawdite’s HDTs and models**. These training solutions leverage insights from WP5, ensuring that learning experiences are **personalised, responsive, and data-driven**, ultimately enhancing worker **performance, safety, and engagement** within the XR5.0 ecosystem.

Figure 1 - WP3 in the XR5.0 Overall Project

2. HUMAN-CENTRIC DIGITAL TWINS IN THE XR5.0 PROJECT

The arising of the Industry 5.0 paradigm and the growing recognition of workers' central role in manufacturing highlights the need for Digital Twins (DTs) that also encompass human representation [1]. As cognitive automation becomes increasingly pervasive and its behaviour often unintelligible to humans, it becomes crucial to **model humans as data-driven agents** and represent their interactions with factory systems to enhance both performance and well-being [2, 3].

However, the absence of a standardized framework for creating DTs forces industrial solution architects to rely on custom, ad-hoc implementations and models [4]. These approaches often lack reusability, scalability, and extensibility, making it challenging to integrate human digital representations into existing DTs, limiting the full realization of the Industry 5.0 paradigm [5]. However, from the original concept of DT introduced in 2012 as “an integrated multi-physics, multi-scale, probabilistic simulation of a flying vehicle or systems” [6], the advent of Industry 5.0 marked a shift in empowering the operators with the skills that will be necessary for future work, making the working environment more inclusive and involving workers in the design and deployment of new industrial technologies, including robotics and AI.

Human-centricity, a pillar of Industry 5.0, emphasizes prioritizing human needs, including safety, health, self-actualization, and personal development, within production processes. In this context, HDTs are proposed as one of the critical methods for empowering operators in smart manufacturing systems [7, 8]. They integrate models fed by dynamic, real-time data with static or quasi-static data, enabling a comprehensive representation of the human entity, the so-called ‘digital avatar’, that aims to revolutionize human-system integration by **embedding human traits into the system's architecture and functionality**.

To gather real-time information, human activities and behaviours must be recorded and compared with historical data, which need to be stored and formalized alongside information describing human characteristics and conditions. In this way, **HDTs can provide digital representations of anthropometric and physiological features, as well as a person's inner state**, including characteristics, medical, emotional, and psychophysical conditions, psychophysical and geospatial parameters, and contextual, functional, and decision models. Digitizing the person will facilitate including considerations on human workers in an Industry 5.0 production systems, addressing communication, simulation, and scheduling [9, 10].

Figure 2 provides a visual representation of all the applications that will be discussed in the next sub-chapters.

Figure 2 - HDT Manufacturing Application with and without XR

2.1 Human-Digital Twins in Industry

When implementing HDTs and DTs, it is necessary to evaluate how well the proposed systems meet individual, collective, and production needs or objectives. **DT commonly takes performance-centered interest first**, to reach mass production and improve economic benefits. In contrast, the human-centered paradigm of **HDT requires improving human beings' well-being by respecting their roles, needs, talents, and rights** [11]. Specifically, there exist many performance metrics for DT, such as efficiency, productivity, effectiveness, and profitability. While HDT extends the scope of metrics and measurements for evaluating systems, such as usability, user experience, and avoidance of harm from use. These metrics are particularly valuable in **environments where workers experience continuous stress**, such as manufacturing and healthcare, **where time constraints, high workloads, and repetitive tasks can impact well-being** [12].

HDTs enable real-time tracking of human conditions, helping to detect fatigue, cognitive overload, or ergonomic risks. By integrating physiological and behavioral data, HDTs support adaptive interventions, improving worker safety, comfort, and overall efficiency while maintaining production targets. The following sub-chapters explore key HDT manufacturing applications across different lifecycle phases, from design to production.

2.1.1 HDTs for Design

Ergonomics Analysis

Ergonomic issues represent one of the main factors characterizing the manufacturing working environment. Indeed, in addition to designing a production system according to an ergonomic approach, the working activities need to be continuously monitored, especially when the volume of production varies, causing changes in cycle time and, consequently, changes in working tasks and workload [13]. If work, work environment, and personnel and their interactions are not adequately considered, different disruptions between them can arise, posing multifaceted challenges for the company that may adversely affect personnel through various psychosocial and organizational processes [14].

Suokko et al. research pointed out that it is possible to maintain a high level of productivity without compromising work ability if work is developed using ergonomic methods. On the other hand, if ergonomics is not used when developing work, it can have a negative impact on both the system performance and employee well-being [15].

The HDT has been extensively utilized to analyze work cell ergonomics and optimize workplace layouts by considering worker-specific characteristics, particularly anthropometric data. Numerous examples demonstrate the application of HDTs in offline simulations, where **human models are used to evaluate and refine ergonomic setups before physical implementation**. These simulations allow for adjustments that improve safety, comfort, and productivity while minimizing the risk of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) [16]. In addition to offline applications, advancements in real-time motion capture technologies have enabled **dynamic tracking of worker postures and movements**. These technologies utilize systems such as marker-based or markerless motion capture tools to compute ergonomic indices in real time. For example, wearable motion capture suits and non-optical systems have been used to measure joint angles, forces, and postural risks, providing immediate feedback for ergonomic adjustments [17]. Studies have shown that integrating motion capture data into HDTs enhances the ability to monitor and adapt work environments dynamically, ensuring both safety and productivity [18, 19].

Production Planning and Worker Allocation

In labor-intensive production systems, effective worker allocation is a critical factor influencing production rates, as **worker skills and capacity play a central role in determining overall efficiency**. Excluding these elements from production planning can lead to suboptimal performance and inefficiencies. To address these challenges, **dynamic scheduling systems powered by HDTs**, which address common challenges in

labor-intensive industries, such as variability in attendance or mismatches in skills, have been increasingly employed to enhance production planning and worker allocation. **By simulating various scenarios and predicting outcomes, HDTs enable proactive adjustments to schedules or resource allocation.** This capability ensures smoother operations and reduces downtime while prioritizing worker safety and satisfaction.

Worker allocation strategies powered by HDTs also address challenges such as absenteeism or skill mismatches by simulating various scenarios and predicting outcomes. For example, Wang et al. applied digital twin models in low-volume, high-mix production environments to optimize job allocation dynamically [20]. Their findings demonstrated significant improvements in production efficiency by aligning worker capabilities with job requirements in real time. In addition to improving operational efficiency, the use of HDTs in worker allocation fosters a more inclusive and adaptive workplace environment. By continuously monitoring and analyzing workers' physical and cognitive states, HDTs enable organizations to accommodate diverse needs, including those of workers with disabilities or varying levels of expertise [21]. For example, recent studies have shown how **HDTs can support the integration of underrepresented groups into industrial workflows by tailoring role assignments to individual capabilities.** This not only enhances productivity but also aligns with the broader goals of Industry 5.0, which emphasize human-centric and socially sustainable manufacturing practices.

2.1.2 HDTs for Production

Worker Well-Being and Performance Monitoring

In this era of Industry 5.0, when automation has enlarged an individuals' work routine, higher physical and cognitive level is in demand due to the flexibility and adaptation of tasks. Job characteristics and computer anxiety in the production industry discuss this higher level of cognition needed with high workload, increased work pressure, diminished job control, training, and use of new technologies [22]. Thanks to the miniaturization and reduction of costs, **the adoption of wearables and sensors has been growing also in the industrial context to investigate workers' conditions and well-being.** Employee's well-being is a key factor in determining the organization's long-term competitiveness and it is also directly related to production efficiency. **The cumulative effect of positive impacts on the human factor brings economic benefit through productivity increase, scrap reduction and decrease of absenteeism.** Few research works have been recently developed, where workers' physiological data are used to infer the insurgence of phenomena such as fatigue [23, 24] and mental stress [25] which, in turn, have a relevant impact on process performance.

Montini et al. developed a HDT that has been adopted to monitor worker fatigue and mental stress by introducing a physiological monitoring system and a smart decision-maker to adjust the level of support offered through a cobot [7]. Davila-Gonzalez et al. developed a conceptual framework designed to enhance worker safety and well-being in industrial environments, by leveraging the HDT aiming to enhance workers' physical, mental, and emotional well-being in Industry 5.0 contexts; using smart devices and AI, it monitors body composition, stress, sleep, and emotional states while employing personality analysis to identify risks and provide timely interventions [26].

These examples highlight the significant potential of the emerging HDT concept, which integrates multi-source data and AI for continuous monitoring and assessment. By addressing both technical and social challenges, HDTs open new opportunities for improving worker well-being and safety. In fact, from a human factors' perspective, it is crucial to focus on optimizing the development of HDTs in industrial settings and designing their applications to maximize effectiveness and usability.

Human-Robot Collaboration and Adaptive Automation

In recent decades, adaptive control systems have been extensively explored, particularly in the context of incorporating worker-specific features within real-time control loops. These systems aim to dynamically adjust automation processes based on human physiological and cognitive states, thereby enhancing both

safety and efficiency in collaborative environments. For instance, research has demonstrated the integration of psychophysiological markers, such as heart rate variability and task load indices, into adaptive fuzzy models to optimize task allocation between humans and machines. This real-time monitoring and adjustment framework ensures that system safety and performance are maintained even under varying operator workloads or stress levels [27].

When it comes to robot-assisted assembly, numerous studies have focused on the online dynamic allocation of tasks between humans and robots as well as the simulation of robot motion. Dynamic task allocation methodologies often rely on real-time ergonomic assessments and task complexity evaluations to **assign roles that minimize human strain while maximizing efficiency**. For example, algorithms have been developed to predict human ergonomic risks and adaptively allocate tasks to ensure safe working conditions. Additionally, motion planning for robots in shared workspaces has been advanced through simulation techniques that optimize collision-free paths and synchronize robot actions with human activities [28, 29]. In collaborative environments involving human-robot interaction, HDTs are crucial for ensuring **efficient resource distribution**. Research by Wang et al. highlights how **HDTs can facilitate adaptive workforce allocation in human-robot collaborative systems by dynamically assigning roles based on skill levels and workload balance**. This not only enhances productivity but also minimizes risks associated with repetitive strain or cognitive overload [1].

Recent research has explored the integration of HDTs into production systems to optimize task allocation by incorporating real-time data on workers' skills, preferences, and physiological states. For instance, Cutrona et al. proposed extending digital twin frameworks to include human characterization within Asset Administration Shells (AAS) [30]. This approach enables accurate digital representations of workers, facilitating dynamic decision-making processes that consider individual capabilities and preferences. By leveraging such frameworks, production systems can dynamically assign tasks based on workers' current conditions, improving both efficiency and worker satisfaction.

2.2 Human Digital Twins & XR

As described before, HDTs are emerging as a transformative solution in the manufacturing industry, particularly for addressing the challenges of physically demanding tasks. By creating real-time virtual replicas of workers, these systems enable continuous monitoring of physical and physiological conditions to proactively manage worker fatigue, prevent hazardous situations, and adapt workflows to individual needs. On the other hand, XR, which encompasses Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), and Mixed Reality (MR), offers immersive and interactive experiences that further enhance the capabilities of HDTs to create more inclusive, efficient, and adaptive industrial environments. However, it still faces challenges, particularly in usability. For these technologies to be effective, they must integrate seamlessly into workflows without negatively impacting users. Monitoring and adapting XR tools based on user characteristics is essential to ensure their usability and effectiveness. **By leveraging XR in conjunction with the HDT, operators can monitor and enhance productivity while also addressing health-related concerns**. This dual approach not only alleviates potential negative effects of XR but also **promotes enhancements in operational activities, fostering a more productive and human-centered work environment**

HDTs, powered by XR, address many of the applications described in Chapter 2.1 while also transforming manufacturing with new applications such as operator's training & education and remote video collaboration, which will be explored in the next sub-chapters.

XR Powered Ergonomics Analysis

Advancements in motion capture (MoCap) and XR technologies have significantly enhanced ergonomic analysis. Real-time tracking of worker movements using marker-based or markerless systems enables dynamic evaluation of postures and body mechanics, offering immediate feedback to mitigate ergonomic risks. For example, Barkokebas et al. demonstrated the integration of MoCap data with VR for ergonomic risk assessment, improving workstation design and worker safety [31]. Furthermore, AR can provide real-

time feedback by **overlaying ergonomic guidelines or posture corrections onto a worker's view**. It has been used effectively in training workers on proper lifting techniques and safe postures, reducing the risk of musculoskeletal disorders [32].

XR Powered Worker Well-Being and Performance Monitoring

XR technologies, combined with physiological monitoring tools such as eye-trackers, wearables, and cameras, are being used to monitor worker attention, stress levels, and task engagement. For example, eye-tracking has been applied to understand assembly sequences and identify design issues affecting the assembly process. These tools, when integrated with XR, can provide workers with real-time feedback on their performance and help them adapt to changing production conditions [33]. However, XR technologies have varying impacts on workload. Research by Xi et al. found that **AR increases mental demand due to the cognitive effort required to process both physical and augmented information** [34]. In contrast, VR's immersive nature reduces perceived task complexity and does not significantly affect workload dimensions. To balance these effects, a user-centric approach is critical. For example, **adaptive systems (as graphical user interfaces) that combine real-time physiological feedback with XR can help minimize cognitive overload** while improving productivity and worker well-being.

XR Powered Human-Robot Collaboration and Adaptive Automation

XR technologies enable seamless interaction between workers and robotic systems. AR and VR provide intuitive interfaces for workers to communicate with robots, visualize task progress, and receive real-time guidance [35]. For instance, **AR can overlay instructions or visual cues onto a worker's environment**, enhancing precision and reducing errors in collaborative tasks. In fact, XR tools allow for the continuous assessment of cognitive load, stress levels, and physical conditions, enabling real-time adjustments to task assignments. Furthermore, adaptive automation systems leverage XR to dynamically adjust robot behavior based on human input or environmental changes, ensuring flexibility in complex workflows [36]. These technologies not only improve efficiency but also reduce cognitive load by integrating natural gestures and spatial awareness into interactions.

XR Powered Training and Education

In the era of Industry 5.0, the demand for highly skilled workers in manufacturing has significantly increased. XR technology has been widely applied in manufacturing training and education, aiming to enhance workers' skills, ensure safety, and optimize production processes. **XR technologies enable the creation of immersive and interactive training environments that simulate real-world ones**, enabling users to practice and perfect their techniques without the risks associated with live training, while acquiring new skills and to be ready to operate in real scenarios [37]. Abidi et al. assessed a virtual reality-based manufacturing assembly training system with the participants trained using VR committed fewer errors and completed tasks faster in real-world assembly compared to those trained traditionally [38]. Furthermore, the study highlighted the benefits of VR, such as providing a **risk-free, immersive environment for "learning by doing"**, particularly for complex assemblies. Another application case has been provided by Mourtzis et al. that developed an XR-based collaborative platform to enhance engineering education in the context of Industry 5.0 through immersive, hands-on training experiences that improve operator performance, safety, and efficiency [39]. The study highlights the potential of XR technologies to foster innovation, collaboration, and skill development in engineering education while addressing the evolving demands of modern industrial systems.

An aspect that is gaining popularity together with XR applied for training and education is gamification as it enhances user engagement and learning efficiency by the development of different level-based challenges that gradually increasing task complexity keeping users engaged while building their skills incrementally or with scoring systems that motivate learners through rewards and competition [40]. For example, Ulmer et al. proposed an adaptive, gamified VR training system tailored for the manufacturing industry to enable flexible and personalized training sequences [41]. The system automatically adapts to individual users'

skills and performance by adjusting task complexity and providing visual guidance. With the utilisation of key performance indicators (KPIs) such as task time and error rates, the authors were then able to evaluate user performance and refine the training routines.

This application is representing a transformative approach to skill development but there are still few obstacles to overcome as identified by Doolani et al. [42]. The study highlighted the benefits of XR, including improved safety, engagement, and training efficiency in complex or hazardous environments; however, they also noted barriers to adoption, such as hardware limitations, high costs, and the need for better interaction interfaces. A similar study has been carried out by Ortega-Gras et al. that investigated the potential of XR technologies by analyzing current XR hardware and software, reviewing successful use cases, and gathering opinions from European students, teachers, and training organizations [43]. The authors then provided a comprehensive XR training pathway featuring tools like Unity software, HTC Vive Pro headsets, and Microsoft Dynamics 365 Guides. This pathway aims to improve immersive learning experiences while addressing challenges such as funding, accessibility, and technical barriers.

XR Powered Remote Video Collaboration, Control and Maintenance

Applications for remote monitor and control are essential to modern manufacturing because they allow operators to supervise and control machinery from a distance. Even in situations when direct physical engagement with the machinery is impractical, these applications make **use of real-time data transfer and sophisticated user interfaces to guarantee effective and secure operations**. By integrating XR, companies can improve the efficiency and accuracy of equipment maintenance, particularly for complex or hard-to-reach components. XR enables technicians to receive **real-time guidance and visual overlays**, enhancing their ability to perform precise repairs. Additionally, remote experts can provide support, reducing downtime and ensuring maintenance tasks are completed accurately, ultimately boosting equipment reliability and operational efficiency. Remote Video Collaboration, including AR, has been a viable alternative to in-person work for equipment installations, troubleshooting, and training, especially under COVID-19 travel restrictions [44]. Although there are some studies for integrating AR and VR for asymmetric collaboration, supporting visual guidance for effective task assistance remains challenging. Moon et al. proposes an XR-based remote collaboration approach to supporting smart task assistance by reconstructing the 3D virtual space of the local AR environment as a digital twin of the real-world spatial reference and by providing deep learning-based visual guidance, in addition to multimodal gestures such as hand gestures and eye gazing [45]. Thus, a remote VR expert can comprehensively understand and **explore the local working situation and interact with the remote worker** with various interaction metaphors and the VR expert can guide the remote AR worker to perform their tasks more effectively through the step-by-step instructions with deep learning-based visual cues and annotations. Marques et al. present a remote maintenance solution using AR and off-the-shelf mobile technologies to enhance efficiency in Industry 4.0 [46]. The system enables remote collaboration between skilled and unskilled operators through tools like 2D symbols, sketches, and text, avoiding complex 3D models to reduce visual overload. Designed to work under varying network conditions, it was refined based on industrial feedback, leading to features like sketching and optimization for tablets over AR goggles.

The second application is remote control. Yang et al.'s study on a digital-twin-based smart crane provides an example of how these applications are implemented [47]. Real-time control and monitoring of the crane's operations via communication middleware enables operators to see the crane's movements, check its status from a distance, and make any adjustments to improve both operating efficiency and safety. The remote monitor/control application includes a user-friendly interface for viewing operational data, interacting with virtual controls, and executing commands.

Another major application connected with remote video collaboration is maintenance. Aschauer et al. investigated the development and evaluation of an open-source AR remote support tool tailored for industrial maintenance tasks, finding that while AR remote support does not significantly reduce task completion time compared to traditional paper-based instructions, although it substantially decreases error rates (from 53% with paper-based instructions to 13% with AR support) [48]. Furthermore, the

authors highlighted the importance of configurability in AR tools to address diverse use cases and environmental constraints, such as low bandwidth, hands-free operation, and security concerns. Mourtzis et al. developed a real-time AR-based framework for remote maintenance and repair operations [49]; the proposed system enables shop-floor technicians to collaborate with remote expert engineers through live video streaming, AR content creation, and spatial recognition, eliminating the need for predefined AR scenarios.

3. MODELING AND SPECIFICATIONS OF WORKER DIGITAL IMAGES (IPIA)

As part of Task 3.1, the XR5.0 project aims to integrate human factors assessments into XR environments to enhance usability, worker well-being, and overall system efficiency. This involves capturing the **static, semi-static, and dynamic characteristics of industrial workers**, such as physical attributes (e.g., height, weight), level of expertise, emotional states, fatigue levels, and task performance behaviors. The main outcome of this task is a **set of specifications for generating worker digital images** that can be seamlessly integrated into XR applications. These HDTs enable personalization of XR content, workflows, and virtual environments, ensuring a more intuitive and adaptive XR experience.

A key focus of this assessment is to evaluate the human factors influencing how workers interact with XR systems. XR technologies allow users to engage with their digital avatars in real time, facilitating ergonomic improvements, enhanced safety, intuitive training, and more efficient remote collaboration. However, for XR to be truly effective in industrial settings, **real-time monitoring of cognitive workload, stress levels, and user engagement is essential**. By incorporating physiological and behavioral measurements, XR applications can dynamically adapt to the worker's conditions, optimizing performance, well-being, and overall experience [50].

3.1 A Structured Framework for Assessing Human Factors in XR Assisted Tasks

IPIA has developed a structured framework for assessing human factors in XR-assisted tasks. This framework provides a **structured approach for assessing human factors in XR-assisted tasks**. Its primary objective is to enhance the usability, well-being, and efficiency of XR systems in industrial settings by capturing and analyzing worker characteristics such as physical attributes, emotional states, and task performance behaviors. The framework will be applied across the project's pilots to evaluate and optimize XR environments, ensuring they are adaptive, intuitive, and safe for workers.

This framework is a critical component of XR5.0's objective to create human-centric digital twins that adapt to real-time conditions, enhancing user experience, safety, and performance. By embedding human factors into digital twins, the framework supports the project's commitment to **human-centric design, aiming to create adaptive systems that respond to user needs, improve usability, and reduce risks associated with human-machine interaction**. The objectives of the framework can be summarised as follows:

- Provide a structured approach for capturing, analyzing, and representing human factors within XR environments.
- Ensure that human factors are a core element in the development and operation of XR-based systems, rather than an afterthought.
- Facilitate the real-time adaptation of XR environments based on user states, leading to more responsive and supportive systems.

3.1.1 Human-Factors in XR

Several studies in the literature have explored variables related to human factors in the use of VR within the manufacturing sector. Researchers have focused on cognitive skills, trust and acceptance of XR tools, user motivation, participant attitudes, prior experience, cybersickness, physiological responses, presence, and technical performance aspects [51, 52, 53].

Physical and cognitive factors, such as perceived workload, task complexity, information overload, and time pressure, can significantly influence users' performance and the quality of human-machine interaction. To optimize human performance, it is essential to **prevent stressful physical and mental conditions, as well as cognitive underload or overload** [54]. Among these factors, **mental stress** plays a particularly critical role in XR environments due to its substantial impact on cognitive performance, decision-making processes, and overall well-being [55]. In immersive settings, workers often face increased cognitive demands, time pressure, and multisensory integration challenges, which can lead to elevated stress levels. By accounting for mental stress, the **framework provides real-time insights into workers' states**, enabling adaptive XR systems to optimize task performance and minimize stress-related errors or fatigue. While other human

factors—such as physical attributes, expertise, and fatigue—are also considered, mental stress is emphasized due to its direct impact on cognitive ergonomics in XR environments during task execution.

3.1.2 Key Aspects of Mental Stress in XR5.0

Mental stress is conceptualized as a **multi-dimensional construct reflected in physiological, behavioral, and self-reported data**. It refers to an individual's cognitive, emotional, and physiological response to the demands of an XR environment, particularly when interacting with HDTs and performing complex industrial tasks. Mental stress emerges when there is a **perceived imbalance between task demands** (e.g., cognitive load, time pressure, multisensory integration) **and the individual's ability to cope effectively** [56, 57]. Below are key aspects of mental stress in XR5.0:

1. **Cognitive Overload** – XR environments may increase mental workload, requiring workers to process large amounts of spatial, visual, and procedural information in real time.
2. **Emotional Reactivity** – The level of anxiety, frustration, or discomfort caused by immersive experiences, system complexity, or unexpected interactions with digital elements.
3. **Physiological Responses** – Measurable changes in heart rate (HR), heart rate variability (HRV), electrodermal activity (EDA), and pupil dilation that indicate stress levels.
4. **Task-Induced Stressors** – Factors such as precision-based tasks, prolonged XR exposure, simulation sickness, and time constraints that impact worker performance and well-being.
5. **Adaptation & Performance Impact** – XR5.0 aims to assess how stress affects attention, decision-making, and task efficiency, informing real-time system adaptations to optimize user experience and safety.

In addition to mental stress, the framework considers a range of other human factors that influence worker performance and well-being in XR environments. In addition to mental stress, the framework can incorporate a broader spectrum of human factors that impact worker performance and well-being in XR environments. The human factors outlined in this deliverable were prioritized based on the **user stories detailed in Deliverable 6.1 - Use Cases Co-Creation and Pilot Sites Preparation**. As these user stories are further refined—particularly within Task 6.1, which focuses on pilot site preparation—we can identify and characterize additional human factors [58], defining them through specific metrics. These factors may include, but are not limited to:

- **Anthropometric characteristics** (e.g., physical strength, body dimensions, and range of motion)
- **Biomechanical parameters** (e.g., posture dynamics, movement efficiency, and ergonomic analysis)
- **Geospatial representation** (e.g., proximity to equipment, spatial awareness, and hazard recognition)
- **Skill profiles** (e.g., consistency in skill application, proficiency levels, and task-specific expertise)
- **Functional capabilities** (e.g., sensory abilities such as visual acuity, auditory perception, and tactile sensitivity)
- **Task execution behaviors** (e.g., work pace, rhythm, and adherence to procedural steps)
- **Adaptation patterns** (e.g., responsiveness to unexpected situations, problem-solving strategies, and learning curves)

As will be described below, these factors are captured through a combination of **physiological measurements** (e.g., heart rate, electrodermal activity), **behavioral indicators** (e.g., eye-tracking, gaze fixation), and **self-reported measures** (e.g., stress analog scales, user experience questionnaires). By integrating these multi-modal data sources, the framework provides a comprehensive understanding of worker states, enabling personalized and adaptive XR systems that enhance both performance and well-being.

Thus, this framework integrates physiological, behavioral, and self-reported measures. It is designed to be both adaptable and aligned with the broader objectives of the XR5.0 project:

- **Flexibility** – Each pilot can tailor the assessment instruments to focus on the specific parameters most relevant to their evaluation, ensuring that the methodology remains adaptable to different industrial contexts and research priorities.
- **Human-centric approach** – By addressing key challenges in XR deployment, the framework ensures that XR systems are optimized for usability, worker well-being, and overall system efficiency.

By systematically integrating these multi-modal measures into the pilots, the XR5.0 project enhances the personalization and effectiveness of XR applications, ultimately improving user experience, cognitive ergonomics, and workplace safety in immersive environments.

To align with the objectives of Task 3.1, we present a structured approach for measuring human factors in XR environments, emphasizing practical implementation models for technology developers. Specifically, we describe:

1. Key variables and parameters
2. Their significance and application
3. Suitable algorithms or classification methods for implementation

3.2 Measurement of Human Factors in XR Instruments and Phases

Understanding human factors in XR environments requires a structured assessment methodology that captures **individual variations** in physiological, behavioral, and subjective responses. Since **there are no predefined thresholds** that universally indicate whether a worker exhibits a moderate or high level of a given physiological response, we adopt a **three-phase evaluation** approach to ensure a **comprehensive and individualized assessment**.

This methodology allows us to analyze **how human factors evolve across different phases** of XR interaction, rather than relying on arbitrary cut-off points. Specifically, we divide the assessment into:

1. **Baseline Measurement (Pre-Test Phase):** Establishes each participant’s physiological and psychological reference state before XR exposure.
2. **Task Performance Measurement (During XR Interaction):** Captures real-time physiological and behavioral changes in response to the XR environment.
3. **Post-Task Measurement (Recovery & Reflection):** Evaluates how participants recover after XR exposure and records self-reported experiences.

By structuring the measurement process in this way, we can track intra-individual variations, ensuring that any detected changes are interpreted relative to each participant’s baseline rather than applying a one-size-fits-all approach. This is essential for developing personalized algorithms that can dynamically adapt XR environments based on real-time human factors data.

3.2.1 Measurements Instruments

The assessment relies on multiple objective and subjective measurement tools, each capturing critical aspects of user experience, stress, cognitive load, and usability. See *Table 1* for a description of all objective and subjective measurement tools and *Table 2* with a description of the three phases to track user responses before, during, and after XR task performance.

Table 1 - Objective and Subjective Measurement Tools

Category	Measurement	Description
Physiological Measurements	Electrodermal Activity (EDA) [59]	Measures skin conductance response (SCR) and tonic level (SCL), indicating emotional arousal and stress levels in response to XR stimuli.

	Heart Rate (HR) & Heart Rate Variability (HRV) [60]	Tracks beats per minute (BPM) and HRV, assessing stress, cognitive load, and relaxation states.
Visual Behavior Measurements	Eye-Tracking [61]	Records pupil dilation, gaze fixation, and direction, providing insights into cognitive load, attention distribution, and usability of XR interfaces.
Standardized Questionnaires	Presence Questionnaire [62]	Measures the sense of immersion and realism in XR.
	Simulator Sickness Questionnaire (SSQ) [63]	Assesses nausea, oculomotor strain, and disorientation caused by XR exposure.
	NASA-TLX (Task Load Index) [64]	Evaluates perceived workload across six dimensions: mental demand, physical demand, temporal demand, performance, effort, and frustration.
	User Experience Questionnaire (UXQ) [65]	Assesses ease of use, enjoyment, and usability of the XR system.
	Stress Analog Scale (SAS, 1-10) [66]	A simple self-reported tool where participants rate perceived stress levels on a scale from 1 to 10.

Table 2 - Key Phases to Track User Responses before, during, and after XR Task Performance

Phase	Measurements	Description
Pre-Test Phase	Heart Rate (HR) & HRV	Capturing cardiovascular activity at rest to establish a baseline.
	Electrodermal Activity (EDA)	Measuring baseline stress levels through skin conductance response (SCR) and tonic level (SCL).
Visual Behavior Measurements	Stress Analog Scale (SAS, 1-10)	Participants rate their initial stress level on a scale from 1 to 10.
Task Performance Phase	Physiological Measurements: EDA	Monitors stress levels based on skin conductance response (SCR) and tonic level (SCL) during XR interaction.
	Heart Rate & HRV	Tracks BPM and HRV fluctuations, reflecting cognitive load and relaxation states during XR task execution.
	Visual Behavior Analysis: Eye-Tracking	Measures pupil dilation, gaze fixation, and blink rate, assessing cognitive engagement and fatigue during XR interaction.
	Self-Reported Measures: Stress Analog Scale (SAS, 1-10)	Applied at one or multiple points during the task to capture momentary stress perception.
Post-Test Phase	Presence Questionnaire	Measures the sense of immersion and realism in XR after task completion.
	Simulator Sickness Questionnaire (SSQ)	Assesses nausea, oculomotor strain, and disorientation caused by XR exposure.
	NASA-TLX	Evaluates perceived workload across six dimensions: mental demand, physical demand, temporal demand, performance, effort, and frustration.
	User Experience Questionnaire (UXQ)	Assesses ease of use, enjoyment, and usability of the XR system after task completion.
	Stress Analog Scale (SAS, 1-10)	Participants rate their final stress level on a scale from 1 to 10 for comparison with baseline and task performance phases.

3.3 Description of all Indicators

3.3.1 Physiological Indicators

Stress is characterized by a state of heightened physiological arousal, accompanied by emotions with negative valence, resulting from external or internal stressors acting on an individual [67, 68].

The body's response to stress includes autonomic nervous system activation, which manifests through physiological changes such as increased skin conductance (sweating), elevated heart rate (tachycardia), and higher blood pressure [69, 70]. These responses are observed both during and immediately after exposure to a stressful task. However, physiological stress reactions occur not only in negative stress (distress) but also in positive stress (eustress), making it difficult to distinguish between these emotional states based solely on physiological indicators [71]. Physiological signals can provide information about arousal or stress intensity, but they do not capture emotional valence—that is, whether the experience is perceived as harmful or beneficial [72]. Because of this limitation, research suggests that combining physiological measures with psychological and subjective self-reports improves the accuracy and reliability of stress assessment [73].

EDA and HRV are pivotal physiological markers for assessing stress and arousal due to their direct association with the autonomic nervous system's (ANS) responses. EDA measures the electrical conductance of the skin, which varies with sweat gland activity controlled by the sympathetic branch of the ANS. When an individual encounters stressors, sympathetic activation increases, leading to heightened sweat secretion and, consequently, elevated skin conductance levels. This makes EDA a sensitive indicator of emotional and physiological arousal. Studies have demonstrated that EDA effectively reflects sympathetic arousal in response to stressors and other stimuli. **Evaluating both EDA and HRV provides a comprehensive understanding of an individual's autonomic responses to stress.** While EDA captures sympathetic arousal, HRV reflects parasympathetic modulation. The concurrent analysis of these measures offers insights into the dynamic balance between sympathetic and parasympathetic activities, enhancing the **accuracy of stress and arousal assessments**. For instance, combining HRV and EDA metrics has been proposed to assess autonomic function and stress responses more effectively [74].

Electrodermal Activity (EDA)

- **Skin Conductance Level (SCL)** – Represents baseline arousal. Higher SCL peaks correspond to higher stress.
- **Skin Conductance Response (SCR)** – Captures phasic responses to stimuli. Higher SCR peaks correspond to higher stress.

Heart Rate (HR) & Heart Rate Variability (HRV)

- **Beats per Minute (BPM)** – It assesses the number of times the heart beats in one minute. Elevated BPM can indicate stress, anxiety, or excitement due to increased sympathetic nervous system activity.
- **Low-Frequency (LF) and High-Frequency (HF) power**
 - **LF/HF Ratio** – It assesses the balance between the sympathetic (low-frequency, LF) and parasympathetic (high-frequency, HF) branches of the autonomic nervous system. High LF/HF suggests sympathetic dominance and thus a stress response. By defining the LF band (typically 0.04–0.15 Hz) and HF band (typically 0.15–0.4 Hz), it's possible to compute this metric as:

$$LF/HF \text{ Ratio} = \text{Power in LF Band} / \text{Power in HF Band}$$

- **Means Root Mean Square of Successive Differences (RMSSD)** – It assesses the variability between successive heartbeats (specifically, the intervals between consecutive R-peaks in an electrocardiogram, known as RR intervals). Lower RMSSD reflects reduced parasympathetic

activity and higher stress and fatigue, while higher values mean a strong parasympathetic (vagal) tone, which indicates relaxation. It's possible to compute this metric as:

$$RMSSD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (RR_{i+1} - RR_i)^2}{N}}$$

3.3.2 Behavioral Indicators

Behavioral indicators provide valuable insights into a worker's cognitive load, stress levels, and overall engagement in XR environments. Unlike physiological measures, which capture autonomic nervous system activity, behavioral responses **reflect voluntary and involuntary adaptations to cognitive and emotional demands**. This section details three primary behavioral indicators—eye-blinking, gaze fixation, and pupil dilation—which have been widely recognized as reliable proxies for cognitive workload, stress, and fatigue. These indicators are monitored in real time to assess how workers interact with XR environments and to inform adaptive system responses that enhance usability and well-being. By analyzing variations in these behavioral metrics across different phases of XR interaction, we can better understand how users respond to immersive environments and tailor XR applications to optimize cognitive ergonomics and performance.

Eye-Blinking

- **Blink Rate (BR)** – An increased blink rate is often associated with fatigue and stress. Studies have shown that blink rate variability can provide information about cognitive performance and mental fatigue [75]. Stress often leads to an increase in spontaneous blink rate; conversely, during moments of intense focus or attention (e.g., solving a problem or responding to a visual stimulus), blink rate may temporarily decrease.
- **Blink Duration (BD)** – Shorter blink durations may indicate higher cognitive load. Research suggests that changes in blink dynamics, including blink duration, are sensitive to mental fatigue and cognitive processing demands [76].

Gaze Fixation

- **Fixation Duration (FD)** – Longer fixation durations are indicative of higher cognitive load. Increased fixation duration has been linked to tasks requiring deeper cognitive processing [77]. Extended gaze fixation on complex elements suggests that the individual is experiencing difficulty processing information, which may be a sign of elevated stress or cognitive load.

Pupil Dilation

- **Pupil diameter (mm)** – Variations in pupil size are correlated with changes in cognitive load and stress levels. Greater pupil dilation has been observed in response to increased mental effort and arousal [78]. Monitoring pupil dilation provides insights into the individual's cognitive and emotional state, with larger pupil sizes indicating higher levels of stress or cognitive load.

3.3.3 Self-Reported Indicators

Self-reported indicators are crucial tools in assessing subjective experiences and perceptions, particularly in the context of XR environments and operational settings. These indicators provide valuable insights into user immersion, workload, stress levels, and overall user experience, which are essential for optimizing system design and user interaction. *Table 3* outlines several widely used questionnaires, including the Presence Questionnaire, SSQ, NASA-TLX, UXQ, and SAS. Each of these tools is designed to capture specific

¹ RMSSD is calculated using the square root of the mean squared differences of successive RR intervals, expressed in milliseconds. *N* represents the total number of successive differences between RR intervals.

aspects of user experience and physiological responses, offering a structured approach to data collection and interpretation.

These self-reported indicators are among the most commonly utilized in the field, supported by extensive research and validation. For example, the Presence Questionnaire has been widely adopted to measure immersion in virtual environments, while the NASA-TLX is a standard tool for assessing cognitive workload [79]. Similarly, the SSQ is frequently used to evaluate cybersickness symptoms. Additional indicators tailored to the specific needs of each pilot or study can be added. This adaptability ensures that we can comprehensively address the unique requirements of different operational contexts, enhancing the accuracy and relevance of our assessments.

Table 3 - Questionnaires, Structure and Scores

Questionnaire	Purpose	Structure	Score Interpretation
Presence Questionnaire	Measures immersion and realism in XR.	19 items rated on a 7-point Likert scale - 1 = strongly disagree - 7 = strongly agree	Higher scores mean a stronger sense of presence.
Simulator Sickness Questionnaire (SSQ)	Assesses cybersickness symptoms (nausea, oculomotor strain, disorientation).	16 symptoms rated on a 4-point scale - 0 = none - 3 = severe	Higher scores mean a more severe simulator sickness.
NASA-TLX	Evaluates perceived workload during a task.	6 subscales rated on a 20-point scale - 0 = very low - 20 = very high Optional weighting applied.	Higher scores mean a higher perceived workload.
User Experience Questionnaire (UXQ)	Assesses ease of use, enjoyment, and usability of XR systems.	10-20 items rated on a Likert scale - 1 = strongly disagree - 20 = strongly agree	Higher scores mean a more positive user experience.
Stress Analog Scale (SAS, 1-10)	Measures perceived stress levels.	Single-item scale rated - 1 = no stress - 10 = extremely stressed	Higher scores = higher perceived stress.

3.4 Algorithms and Models for Human Factors Classification

Understanding and classifying human factors is essential for optimizing performance, safety, and user experience in various operational and technological environments. This section delves into the algorithms and models used to **analyze and classify human factors**, focusing on within-subject variation across different phases: baseline, task, and post-task. By normalizing metrics to baseline values, we can highlight deviations that occur during task execution and recovery periods. This approach allows for a more personalized analysis, accounting for individual differences in physiological and behavioral responses.

Key methods include **baseline normalization**, which adjusts all metrics to an individual's baseline state, and the computation of variance and stability metrics to quantify fluctuations across phases. These techniques provide valuable insights into the stability and variability of human responses, enabling more accurate classification and interpretation of human factors. By leveraging these algorithms and models, we can better understand the impact of tasks and interventions on human performance and well-being, ultimately leading to more effective and tailored solutions in various applications.

Baseline Normalization

Normalize all metrics to baseline values for individual subjects to highlight deviations during task and post-task phases, using the following formula:

$$\Delta Metric = \frac{BaselineValue - PostTaskValue}{BaselineValue} * 100^2$$

A positive result ($\Delta Metric > 0$) indicates that the metric decreased during or after the task compared to baseline. A negative result ($\Delta Metric < 0$) indicates that the metric increased during or after the task compared to baseline. A result of zero ($\Delta Metric = 0$) means no change occurred.

Variance and Stability Metrics

The within-subject variance formula is used to quantify stability or fluctuation across phases. It calculates the average variance within subjects by summing the squared deviations of each observation from its subject’s mean, dividing by the degrees of freedom. It is calculated as:

$$Variance = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{j=1}^n (y_{ij} - \bar{y}_i)^2}{k(n - 1)}$$

Where:

- y_{ij} is the j -th observation for subject i ,
- \bar{y}_i is the mean of all observations for subject i ,
- k is the number of subjects,
- n is the number of measurements per subject

Alternative calculations are possible like the change from baseline to task, the change from task to post-task and the return-to-baseline comparison (baseline vs. post-task).

Key aspects of each metric

To effectively monitor and analyze physiological and behavioral metrics in operational settings, it is essential to understand the key aspects of each metric, including its source of data, type of data, input format, and pre-processing requirements. *Table 4* provides a comprehensive overview of these aspects for metrics such as EDA, HR, Heart HRV, RMSSD, Blink Rate, Pupil Dilation, and Gaze Fixation Duration. This information serves as a guide for operational teams to ensure accurate data collection, processing, and interpretation in real-world applications.

Table 4 - key Aspects of each Physiological and Behavioral Metric for Operational Guidance

Metric	Source of Data	Type of Data	Input Format	Pre-Processing
EDA (SCL μS)	Skin conductance sensors (e.g., fingers or wrists)	Continuous time-series (μ S)	- Time-stamped EDA values - Sampling rate (e.g., ≥ 1 Hz)	- Noise reduction - Separation into tonic (baseline) and phasic components
HR (BPM)	PPG or ECG sensors	Time-series of beats per minute (BPM)	- Timestamped HR values - Optional annotations for peaks/irregularities	- Artifact filtering (e.g., movement noise)
HRV (LF/HF Ratio)	PPG or ECG recordings	Spectral HRV metrics (LF/HF ratio)	- LF/HF ratio values - Timestamps	- Extraction of LF/HF components using Fourier or wavelet transforms
RMSSD (ms)	ECG or PPG sensors	Time-series RMSSD values	- RMSSD values annotated with timestamps	- Artifact removal to ensure clean R-R intervals

² The formula is used to calculate the percentage change of a metric (e.g., heart rate, blood pressure, or any other physiological or performance measure) during a task or post-task phase relative to its baseline value.

Blink Rate (/min)	Eye-tracking cameras or wearable devices	Blink count per minute	- Aggregated blink count over predefined intervals (e.g., 1 minute)	- Blink detection via image processing or infrared algorithms
Pupil Dilation(%)	Eye-tracking cameras with infrared illumination	Percentage change in pupil size	- Time-stamped pupil diameter values - Baseline value for relative comparison	- Normalization against baseline - Filtering of artifacts (e.g., eye closure)
Gaze Fixation Duration(s)	Eye-tracking systems detecting gaze fixation points	Duration of gaze fixation (in seconds)	- Time-stamped fixation durations - Coordinates or labels for Areas of Interest (AOIs)	- Aggregation and segmentation based on task-relevant AOIs

Statistical approaches

The following approaches will be used to interpret data retrieved from project experiments:

Correlation Analysis (Pearson/Spearman), **ANOVA** (Analysis of Variance) or **Mixed-Effects Models** (allows for within-subject variations to be analyzed, considering that stress responses can fluctuate dynamically over time rather than being static thresholds).

Regression Models (Linear & Logistic Regression) can help model the continuous relationship between stress markers (e.g., HRV, pupil dilation) and reported stress levels and logistic regression can be useful when categorizing stress into binary or multi-level classes (e.g., low vs. high stress), based on physiological and behavioral predictors

Machine learning (ML) procedures can also be implemented. They can process physiological (e.g., HRV, EDA, pupil dilation) and behavioral (e.g., eye blink rate, gaze fixation) metrics to detect patterns and deviations indicative of stress. Rather than relying on predefined cut-offs, ML models can learn from collected data to establish personalized stress indicators, improving classification accuracy.

3.5 Plan for the Next Period

Define Data Requirements and Formats:

- Work with partners to define the specific data outputs from the mental stress framework (e.g., stress levels, cognitive load, fatigue) and determine how they will be structured and formatted for integration into the Clawdite platform.

Data Preprocessing and Normalization:

- Before sending data to the platform, ensure that it is preprocessed and normalized (e.g., baseline normalization for physiological metrics like HRV and EDA) to ensure consistency and accuracy.
- Implement data validation checks to filter out noise or outliers that could affect the quality of the digital twins.

Map Data to Digital Twin Attributes:

- Define how the human factors data will map to the attributes of the digital twins. For example:
 - Stress levels could influence the worker’s virtual avatar (e.g., showing signs of fatigue or stress).
 - Cognitive load data could adjust the complexity of tasks assigned to the worker in the XR environment.
- Ensure that the platform can dynamically update these attributes based on incoming data.

Test the Integration:

- Conduct rigorous testing to ensure that the integration works as intended. This includes:
 - Testing the API for reliability, latency, and error handling.

- Validating that the digital twins are updated correctly based on the incoming data.

Implement Security and Privacy Measures:

- Since the data being integrated includes sensitive physiological and behavioral information, it is crucial to implement robust security and privacy measures.
- Ensure that the API and platform comply with relevant data protection regulations (e.g., GDPR) and that data is encrypted during transmission and storage.

Potential Challenges and Mitigation Strategies:

Data Compatibility Issues:

- Different devices and sensors may produce data in varying formats. To address this, develop a standardized data schema for the API and provide guidelines for partners on how to format their data.
- Real-Time Data Latency:
 - Real-time data streaming may introduce latency, which could affect the responsiveness of the XR environment. Optimize the API and platform infrastructure to minimize delays.
- Scalability:
 - As the number of users and data sources grows, the platform must be able to scale accordingly. Use cloud-based solutions and distributed computing techniques to ensure scalability.
- User Adoption:
 - Ensure that the integration is user-friendly and that stakeholders (e.g., workers, managers) are trained on how to use the platform effectively.

4. FRAMEWORK FOR PERSONAL DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYTICS (UNP)

The personal data collection process was designed to be built along the already existing Clawdite Platform. This human-centered platform characterizes workers and their production environments and supports the creation of HDTs that provide scientifically robust foundations and ready-to-use packages for instantiating HDTs. These packages include human-centered aspects such as interactions, events, software-based simulations and predictions. All the details of the Clawdite Platform are described in Chapter **Error! Reference source not found.** of this deliverable.

As *Figure 3* shows, the data collection process is divided into two dimensions – **human and machine**.

The human dimension collects data from the worker through the BLE Watch and Wear OS Watch, which uses the software of the Wearable Companion App, and through the Eye Tracker, which uses the Eye Tracker Adapter software. On the other hand, the machine dimension collects data from sensors, robots, etc. that humans interact with, through the AAS.

The Clawdite Platform receives data from the Wearable Companion App, Eye Tracker Adapter software and AAS, to collect data from the physical world. This data can then be used to extract relevant insights about both humans and machines, and feed into Digital Twins to create a virtual representation of the factory environment.

Figure 3 - Personal Data Collection Process

Human dimension

The focus of the human dimension is the workers' physiological measures. At this stage of the project, the two major physiological parameters considered are the heart rate and the eye tracking.

Heart rate, along with other metrics, can be measured using wearable devices such as smartwatches and sports bands. The approach ensures maximum compatibility with wearables and smart devices. Similarly, eye tracking is performed using an eye-tracking device to collect information from the worker, such as:

- Eye movements:
 - Fixations – Points where the eyes pause to focus.
 - Saccades – Rapid movements between fixations.

- Smooth pursuits – Following moving objects.
- Microsaccades – Small involuntary movements during fixation.
- Gaze metrics:
 - Gaze position – Exact point of focus.
 - Gaze duration – Time spent on an object/area.
 - Gaze path – Sequence and direction of visual exploration.
- Pupil metrics:
 - Pupil diameter – Reflects cognitive load and emotional arousal.
- Blink dynamics
 - Blink rate – Frequency of blinking indicates cognitive load or fatigue.
 - Blink duration – Longer blinks may reflect reduced attention.

This information enables the analysis of the user focus and engagement with virtual elements, optimize interface design based on gaze patterns, measure cognitive load in immersive tasks and assess interactions in dynamic virtual entrainments.

Machine dimension

To make sure that the personal data collection process will support the largest number of entities possible, on the machine dimension, the Clawdite Platform was expanded to directly support the collection of data provided by Asset Administration Shells.

The AAS is a standardized digital abstraction layer that represents industrial assets, facilitating data exchange, interoperability, and integration within an Industry 4.0 ecosystem. It provides a structured approach for accessing, managing, and processing asset data across heterogeneous and distributed systems, ensuring resilience against failures and cyber threats. It is composed of two core components:

- **The manifest** – A structured management information base (MiB) that provides a standardized description of an asset, organized into:
 - Header, which contains administrative metadata.
 - Body, which is structured into sub-models, where each sub-model defines a specific view or property set of the asset.
- **The component manager** – Responsible for handling requests and managing interactions within the AAS framework. This component is capable of processing incoming requests to access or modify asset properties, managing the execution logic for asset-related computations and ensuring consistency and correctness in the exchange of asset data.

In terms of communication interfaces, AAS enables seamless data exchange through external interface (Inter-AAS & Application Communication) and internal interface (Physical Asset Integration). The external interface implements REST API for request/reply-based communication, supports message-based communication patterns for event-driven interactions and ensures compatibility with other AAS instances, platforms, and external applications. The internal interface provides vendor-specific protocols for interfacing with physical assets, handles real-time data acquisition and synchronization between digital and physical layers, and enables protocol translation for seamless integration with diverse industrial equipment.

AAS follows a hexagonal architecture, ensuring flexible, modular, and maintainable system design. In this regard, the external-facing APIs allow structured interactions with applications, platforms, and other AASs. The internal logic consists of one or more ports defining generic operations for data processing and asset control. Finally, the adapters handle interactions from external systems and requests from AAS to external applications/devices.

The specific AAS supported in this personal data collection process is the NOVAAS.

The AAS enables seamless interoperability with existing AAS implementations, including Noise Sensors like the UNPARALLEL Sound Pressure Level (SPL) Meter and OPC-UA Robots. This means that virtually any OPC-UA-compliant machine can be integrated. Additionally, the AAS framework allows the development of new

AAS models by the community, ensuring continuous expansion and adaptability to evolving industrial needs.

4.1 Digital Twin Collection Adapters

The objective of this chapter is to explain how data from humans and machines is going to be integrated with the Clawdite Platform. Both data sources need to be integrated using **adapters**, but human data integration is done with a different approach than machine data integration. These two approaches are going to be detailed in the sections below, with diagrams, tables and architecture designs.

4.1.1 Wearable Data Acquisition - Clawdite

One important representation in modern Industry 5.0 industrial components are the human entities. Since industry 5.0 is the main contributor for assigning human in a key role, by implementing mechanisms of continuously monitoring humans, such as using wearable data acquisition devices, allows to collect data that can be used to extract more and deeper insights of the workers wearing them. This approach has also been adopted in XR5.0, where human entities are being virtualized in workers through the data collected from the wearable devices. A worker’s representation can be constructed by using a collection of multiple devices and with the corresponding collected metrics.

The Clawdite Platform is utilized for **data ingestion and factory data analysis**. A data collection system such as a smartphone app can be used to collect and stream data collected from sensing-capable devices into the Clawdite Platform. The process of acquiring human-related data, preparing and sending it to the Clawdite platform involves multiple steps and the activities. The flow of the process is represented in the diagram present in *Figure 4*.

Figure 4 - Wearable Data Acquisition Flow

To start a data stream, the user needs to initiate her/his session, achieved when the user presents her/his identity to the companion app. When the session is initiated with success, the data stream begins and the association of it, with the user who initiated, is secured. This step also allows the system to **identify what measurements should be recorded** considering what specific worker started the session and what sensors are available in the wearable device(s) on the user. Metrics to be collected may also vary **based on the worker’s task**, meaning that even if the devices on the worker are capable of collecting more types of metrics, only are collected the ones identified as relevant for the given task. The worker’s metadata for the selected activity is sent to the smart watch.

When collecting data from a wearable device, there are two approaches that are used to connect the wearable device to the smartphone. One is to connect to a device using the standard protocol of Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE), namely the Generic Attribute Profile API, to access device information. The other is to the device companion app on smartphone/tablet provided by the device manufacturer. In this second option is also included the scenario where a pair of apps Watch/Smartphone is developed.

For the first one, to aid the management of BLE connections, a bridge app can be used to handle the connection with devices via BLE. As the bridge it was used the open source “Gadgetbridge” application, where it does all the pairing and data connection to the BLE device and exposes its communications to any other app in the smartphone. The XR app, retrieves these messages through the Android Intent mechanism. The intent mechanism consists in a transmission of messaging objects, in this case, sent by the smartwatch containing the desired characteristics to be measured and the correspondent measurements values, such as heat rate, skin temperature, etc. If the messages arrive with success, it’s sent to the Clawdite platform.

While this approach theoretically provides a generic access to all the devices implementing the BLE protocol, in practice it is limited to the features that the device manufacturer exposes over BLE. Some may not expose all the functionalities over BLE and other may expose but not used the characteristics defined in the standard. Some advanced functionalities also may not have a valid mapping to the BLE standard which may present a serious limitation, depending on the devices used and the information requested.

Table 5 contains a collection of brands that has smartwatches compatible with BLE communication through “Gadgetbridge”.

Table 5 - Brands compatible with BLE

Amazfit	Asteroid OS	Banlejs	Casio	Colmi
Fitpro	Fossil	Garmin	Hama	Hplus
Huawai Honor	Lenovo	Mykrono	Nothing	Pebble
Pine64	Sony	SMA	Wasp OS	Withings
Xiaomi				

For the companion app, the approach selected is to develop an app for the wearable, developed to be executed on top of Google Wear OS and an Android app working together. By using such a pair of apps, is possible to implement fine graining control over the measurements, making it possible to have a fast-paced measurements of the metrics. This allows to have a much more precise snapshot of the worker behavior. This approach uses OS-level APIs, exposed both by the Wear OS and Android OS, to create a dedicated communication where both pieces of software can coordinate the start of collection of data, share specific configurations and sent/receive information.

In both approaches the Android App has the role of initiation all the needed processes, such as identify the worker, setup the watch to start, and stream the data to the platform, where the watch collects the measurements from observing specific characteristics of the worker and send it to the phone app.

When the session is started, the wearable will start recording the values, sending it to the companion app connected to, which by it turn will send it to the to the Clawdite Platform through MQTT. The smartphone app is going to be responsible to handle the data formatting and the association of the streamed data with the user recurring to the identification needed to start the session. When the data is available at the Clawdite Platform it can be presented on **Grafana Dashboard** for data visualization.

4.1.2 AAS- Clawdite

In modern Industry 4.0 industrial environments, the AAS plays a fundamental role in industrial process monitoring and control by providing manufacturers with a comprehensive framework for designing and developing standardized, interoperable digital twins. This approach has also been adopted in XR5.0, where

physical assets such as robots, collaborative robots, machines, and sensors have been virtualized using the AAS standard. Specifically, the process of designing and developing an AAS follows these necessary steps:

1. Type 1 Passive AAS definition:
 - a. Serves as a digital twin or digital image of a physical asset.
 - b. Captures static and descriptive information (e.g., model specifications, documentation, and asset identity).
 - c. Aligned with the AAS meta-model as specified by the Industrial Digital Twin Association (IDTA).
 - d. Uses a structured data model with submodels to describe properties like asset type, lifecycle information, and metadata.
 - e. Information is typically manually updated or periodically synchronized, without continuous operational monitoring.
2. Type 2 and 3 Reactive/Proactive AAS implementation:
 - a. Moves beyond static descriptions by embedding live operational and real-time production data.
 - b. Enables dynamic asset management, decision-making, and event-driven operations.
 - c. Integrates sensor and machine data using real-time interfaces.
 - d. Supports bidirectional communication, allowing assets to:
 - i. Send operational data.
 - ii. Receive commands and adjustments.

Table 6 provides an overview of the key differences between the different types of AAS.

Table 6. Key differences between the Different Types of AASs

Feature	Type 1 Passive AAS	Types 2 & 3 Reactive/Proactive AAS
Data Type	Static, descriptive	Dynamic, operational, real-time
Interaction Model	Read-only, manual updates	Bidirectional (read/write), event-triggered
Protocols	File-based or HTTP API	HTTP REST API + MQTT for real-time updates
Use Case	Asset documentation, identification	Real-time monitoring, control, optimization
Example	Digital twin of a machine’s specs	Live production monitoring, predictive maintenance

Therefore, the standardized AAS meta-model has been used to define the “digital image” of physical assets (i.e. Type 1 Passive AAS). To move from passive to a proactive AAS, the NOVA Asset Administration Shell has been employed. This tool embeds the “digital image” of the asset and link it to operational and real-time production data accessible by using a standard HTTP REST API and/or MQTT event-based communication (i.e. Types 2 and 3 Reactive/Proactive AAS).

Within this framework, the Clawdite Platform has been utilized for data ingestion and factory data analysis. To enable seamless integration between AAS and the Clawdite Platform, the architecture presented in *Figure 5* has been designed. The figure illustrates a simplified version of the Clawdite Platform, highlighting the key functionalities used by the Clawdite AAS Manager.

The Clawdite AAS Manager is the central component of the proposed architecture, positioned between the Clawdite Platform and the AAS ecosystem. It is responsible for managing the registration and de-registration of AAS instances within the Clawdite Platform. Specifically, it handles Birth and Close messages from AAS instances, generates the required Clawdite descriptors by mapping and populating Clawdite entities with data extracted from the standardized AAS Nameplate submodel, and subsequently registers or deregisters AAS instances within the platform.

Once an AAS instance is registered, the Clawdite AAS Manager is responsible for:

1. Monitoring the registered AAS to detect any unexpected disconnections.
2. Consuming and streaming real-time measurements to the platform via the Clawdite MQTT broker.

To perform these functions, the component relies on an external service called the Collecting Agent, which ensures that events from all AAS instances available on the local network (LAN) are streamed to the Clawdite AAS Manager.

Figure 5 - AAS-Clawdite Designed Architecture

Therefore, the Clawdite AAS Manager provides the following set of functionalities:

1. AAS Birth/Close Handler: it is responsible for creating and closing communication from the AASs that are deployed in LAN. Beside the AAS registration, the component allows for both “graceful” and “hard” disconnect of the AAS and triggers appropriate application processes and logics to de-

register the AAS from the Clawdite Platform. As part of the component there is also the Model Transformer and Topic generation that works during the registration activity. The functional module is responsible for collecting both static and dynamic assets (currently included in the Nameplate submodel and OperationalData submodel) and applying predefined transformation rules to align concepts between the source and the target meta-model (Clawdite entity model). Additionally, it properly configures the Collecting agent.

2. Data Streamer: it is responsible to collect data from the Collecting Agent and to transform the data in a format that is compatible with the expected Clawdite measurements and topics.
3. Entity Registration Proxy: it serves as a communication layer between the Clawdite AAS Manager and the external API exposed by the Clawdite Platform. The key functionalities include API request forwarding, response handling, as well as error handling and authentication.

The development of the Clawdite AAS Manager follows the design choices presented in *Table 7*.

Table 7 - Design Choice table for the Clawdite AAS Manager Component

Design Choice	Key Benefits
AAS compliance	Standardized API interface
	Already defined generic Meta-model for describing component internal data structures
	Seamless integration with third-party software
Event-based communication	Scalability and system decoupling
	Asynchronous communication
	Real-time responsiveness

According to the table, the component has been designed as an AAS. This decision allows the use of the generic AAS meta-model to structure its internal data, enabling the representation of the network topology while leveraging the already defined and standardized REST API. Additionally, event-based communication is employed to facilitate the streaming of real-time measurements from registered AAS instances to the Clawdite Platform.

The Clawdite AAS Manager can also generate internal events when specific conditions are met. For example, events may be triggered when a new AAS is attached or when an AAS experiences a "hard" disconnection.

Figure 6, Figure 7, and Figure 8 illustrate the process view of the designed component, depicting the runtime behavior of the Clawdite AAS Manager using a Triggering Relationship model. This model visualizes how events initiate processes or actions within the component, offering insight into its dynamic behavior. It highlights how the component consumes, processes, and produces events.

The three modeled processes focus on:

1. The registration (or Birth process) of an AAS within the Clawdite Platform;
2. The graceful disconnection of an AAS from the Clawdite Platform; and
3. The hard disconnection of an AAS from the Clawdite Platform.

Figure 6 - Clawdite AAS Manager Birth Process Flow

Figure 7 - Clawdite AAS Manager Close Process Flow

Figure 8 - Clawdite AAS Manager Hard Close Process

Finally, upon completing the registration process, a new AAS is added to the Clawdite Platform. The Clawdite AAS Manager then consumes AAS Operational Events, processes them by mapping AAS topics to Clawdite Streaming Service topics, and routes them to the Clawdite. Figure 9 illustrates this process.

Figure 9 - Clawdite AAS Manager Runtime Process Flow

4.2 Results and Findings

This chapter has the objective of showing the results and findings obtained in the work developed for this demo, demonstrated at the General Assembly meeting held on February 5, 2025, in Bremen. The work developed for the demo is intended to solve the integration problem between the entities present in a factory and the Clawdite Platform.

Since in a factory there are two types of entities, those being humans and machines, two different approaches are needed to handle both different sources of data. To demonstrate the integration with the Human actors, a smartwatch capable of collecting heart rate measurements was used. On the other hand, to demonstrate how to integrate the machines with the Clawdite Platform, the Unparallel Sound Pressure Level sensor (UNP-SPL) was used as a source of data.

For the human integration approach, it resulted in a webapp QR code generator, to simulate each individual identification that would be used in a real scenario. I also resulted in an Android app that's going to be used as a companion app in combination with the pineTime smartwatch. The Android app has the role to authenticate the user by reading the QR code, to receive the smartwatch data stream and inject it into the Clawdite Platform.

4.2.1 Demo Wearable - Clawdite

This demo had the objective of showing the integration of the developed personal data collection using a wearable device to monitor heart rate with the Clawdite Platform. This scenario is an opportunity to enhance working conditions, which, in turn, is expected to boost factory productivity and improve the overall satisfaction of everyone involved. The benefit of this integration means that workers data can be collected automatically and sent to the Clawdite Platform to be analyzed in further steps to obtain useful insights about the workers conditions.

For the presentation some assumptions were made. For example, the smartwatch and the smartphone are already connected before the start of the demo. Also, since all the information related to the Digital Twins are stored in the Clawdite Platform, the virtual factories and the workers were all already created. A factory named "GA Bremen" was used, along with a worker for every physically present participant, plus two additional workers to account for any unforeseen circumstances, resulting in a total of 44 workers, each linked to the newly created factory. Essentially every element created was represented by an UUID. All these ID's can be accessed through Clawdite API in <https://xr50.Clawdite.spslab.ch/docs/>.

For the presentation a webapp was developed that provides a list of workers and their UUIDs in the form of QR codes to simulate the workers identification for each user. That webapp can be accessed in <https://worker.xr50.demos.unparallel.pt/>.

It was also developed an Android app able to read the QR code and initiate the worker session. This supports the initial step of the demo where the worker is identified, and all the collected information will be associate with its UUID and will be ready to be visualized in the worker's dashboard, available on Grafana dashboards (more details about the dashboards are provided in Chapter **Error! Reference source not found.**).

To better explain the demo let us consider the following scenario. A worker arrived at work, a factory where this project solution is implemented, and he is getting ready to start. To enable the manager to analyze his performance and optimize anything that's not optimized to maximize the productivity and the well-being of workers, the workers are requested to use the wearables and a smartphone while they perform the assigned job. These wearables are equipped with sensors that are going to read physiological metrics. Each worker will have an identification card that allows the worker to authenticate themselves in the companion app through scanning the QR code on the card, as presented in *Figure 10*. This identification contains information about the physical user and the corresponding digital twins, so the companion app can rightly link the data being read with the worker digital twin.

Figure 10 - Worker scanning QR code

When the authentication is successfully done, while these wearable devices are recording the physiological measurements from the worker, the datasets are sent to the Clawdite Platform in real time while the worker is doing his normal job as usual, represented in *Figure 11*. The collected data in the Clawdite Platform can be represented in a dashboard for visual support. Furthermore, the available data enables further analysis about the state of mind, allowing it to differentiate what tasks the workers are more relaxed or stressed to do, or what the worker perceives as easy or hard, simple or confusing. This could help the team to adapt the environment and plan programs to help all the collaborators to achieve their best performance.

Figure 11 - Data being sent to Clawdite Platform

Demo implementations

To represent the personal card identification of the workers, as mentioned before, a webapp was developed to help simulate the real factory context flow. The webapp consists of a dropdown, as shown in *Figure 12*. Interacting with the dropdown opens a list with all the physically presented participants identification. The list provides a filter by username to ease the searching with each participant name and company acronym.

Figure 12 - Webapp for selecting user to be authenticated

When an identification option is selected, a QR code is generated, as shown in Figure 13, while also showing the name and the company acronym, allowing to easily verify if the information is correct. The QR code is scanned by the workers to login through the smartphone app.

Figure 13 - Webapp with generated QR Code

The QR code generated on the webapp encodes a JSON with the following information presented in Table 88.

Table 8 - JSON fields stored in QR code

Field	Description
Name	Name of the user associated with worker
WorkerID	UUID to identify a specific worker
FactoryID	UUID to identify a specific worker
Company acronym	Acronym of the company name
Company name	Full name of the company

Considering that each user will have their own QR code, to read this information, an Android app was developed that is going to make the login if the QR code reading is successful. The smartwatch chosen to

stream the data in this demo was the pineTime that needs a bridge app to connect to it and collect the data to be sent to the companion Android app. This bridge app is called “Gadgetbridge” and it connects to the smartwatch through BLE. After the reading of the QR identification is when the data streaming begins and it’s injected on Clawdite Platform, making it possible to identify whose data is being recorded and sent.

The smartphone app is composed of two windows. The first window, shown in *Figure 14*, presents a button that opens the camera for QR scanning. When the QR code is read, content from it is extracted and the user navigates to the second window.

Figure 14 - Android app login screen

In the second window, shown in *Figure 15*, is presented the information the user can see after authenticating. Here, worker information is shown, including information as the username and company name. A logout button is present, enabling the user to end the current session and navigate back to the first window.

Figure 15 - Android app user authenticated screen

When a user is authenticated, the Android app is ready to receive the data from the smartwatch. While data is being sent to the Clawdite Platform, a visual support is useful to ease the acknowledgement of the successful data receiving’s and for a better and easier extraction of insights of the data received.

An example of a visualization is depicted in *Figure 16* The HR measurements received from the users end is being presented using time-series and distribution charts, while important KPIs as the current measurement, minimum, maximum, average and workload intensity are presented numerically.

Figure 16 - Dashboard with the worker’s data

4.2.2 Demo SPL – AAS - Clawdite

To showcase the integration between the AAS and Clawdite Platform, as well as the central role of the Clawdite AAS Manager, a live demo was prepared and presented at the General Assembly meeting held on February 5, 2025, in Bremen.

The demo set-up consisted of the following main actors:

- A physical asset – Unparallel Sound Pressure Level sensor (UNP-SPL) – and a type 1 AAS that describes the digital image of the asset.
- An instance of an operational AAS – based on NOVAAS – to deliver a type 2 and 3 UNP-SPL-AAS.
- An instance of the Clawdite AAS Manager connected on the same LAN of the UNP-SPL-AAS.
- A running instance of the Clawdite Platform.
- A simple dashboard for showing UNP-SPL-AAS data streamed to the Clawdite Platform by means of the Clawdite AAS Manager.

Figure 17 shows the physical view of the demo set-up focusing on the physical assets used, computational resources, communication networks, and locations.

Figure 17 - Physical View of the demo set-up

The demo was implemented under the assumptions that:

- The UNP-SPL-AAS has at least two submodels, namely:

- Nameplate: it is a standardized submodel template designed to provide essential nameplate information about an asset in a digital and interoperable way.
- Operational Data: it is a custom submodel used to include operational data that can be collected from the specific physical asset.
- A Factory Entity was already created within the Clawdite Platform and its UUID is used for linking the Clawdite AAS Manager to the Factory.

During the demonstration, live data from the UNP-SPL device was collected by the Clawdite AAS Manager and streamed to the Clawdite Platform. To ensure a continuous flow of data, the workflow shown in *Figure 6* was first executed. In this process, the UNP-SPL-AAS sent a “birth” message to the Clawdite AAS Manager, which then used the information from the “Nameplate” and “OperationalData” of the UNP-SPL-AAS to create all the necessary entities within the Clawdite Platform. Additionally, the Clawdite AAS Manager configured the Collecting Agent to dynamically include all UNP-SPL-AAS topics for monitoring. Entities like “Device Model” and “Measurement Descriptor” and “Factory Entity” were created using the exposed Clawdite Platform API available at <https://xr50.Clawdite.spslab.ch/docs/#/>. *Table 9* and *Table 10* shows how submodels have been used to fill Clawdite entities.

Table 9 - Mapping between AAS submodels and Clawdite entities

Submodel	Clawdite Entity	API Operation
Nameplate	Device Model	
Manufacturer Product Designation	Name	POST /api/v1/device-model
Manufacturer Product Family	Description	
Manufacturer Name	Brand	
Operational Data	Measurement Descriptor	
idShort	Name	POST /api/v1/measurement-descriptor
Description.Text	Description	

Table 10 - Registered UNP-SPL-AAS properties (in Operational Data) as “Measurement Descriptor”

Property 1	
idShort	LAS
Description	represents the Slow measurement of time weighting. Has an associated time constant of 1 second
Property 2	
idShort	LASmin
Description	minimum value of the Slow measurement in the currently time window
Property 3	
idShort	LASmax
Description	maximum value of the Slow measurement in the currently time window
Property 4	
idShort	LAF
Description	represents the Fast measurement of time weighting. Has an associated time constant of 0.125 seconds
Property 5	
idShort	LAFmin
Description	minimum value of the Fast measurement in the currently time window

Property 6	
idShort	LAFmax
Description	maximum value of the Fast measurement in the currently time
Property 7	
idShort	LAEq
Description	Equivalent continuous is the average of sound pressure level

Finally, once all the Clawdite entities were created, the workflow shown in *Figure 9* was executed. During this process, the Clawdite AAS Manager consumed the live data streamed by the UNL-SPL-AAS, adapted its format, and routed it to the Clawdite Platform. Section 5.5 introduces a dashboard that displays UNP-SPL-AAS data streamed by the Clawdite AAS Manager to the Clawdite Platform.

4.3 Plan for the Next Period

At the time of this deliverable, the plan for the next period is divided into three major steps – two on the human dimension and one on the machine dimension:

- **Human dimension:**
 - Wear OS – Enable the support for the Wear OS application to address compatibility limitations with certain smartwatch brands that are not currently supported by the BLE Bridged app, such as Google, Samsung, Mobvoi, OnePlus, Oppo, Citizen, Tag Heuer, Diesel or MontBlanc. By incorporating Wear OS support, the system can extend its reach to a wider range of devices, increasing market coverage and providing users with more flexibility in choosing wearable technology. This enhancement ensures broader accessibility, improved user experience, and greater interoperability within the smartwatch ecosystem.
 - Eye Tracker – Enable the integration of eye-tracking devices, such as the Pupil Labs system used by IPIA, to enhance data collection capabilities. This integration will allow the extraction of additional biometric and behavioral metrics, complementing previously described measurements. Specifically, it will support the analysis of eye movements, gaze metrics, pupil metrics, and blink dynamics, providing deeper insights into cognitive load, attention, and human-machine interaction.
- **Machine dimension:**
 - OPC-UA – Extend the adoption of AAS by enabling seamless integration with industrial systems, particularly through standardized support for OPC-UA. This ensures that a wide range of OPC-UA-compliant machines, including sensors, robots, and other automation devices, can be easily incorporated into the AAS ecosystem. By providing a generic OPC-UA interface, AAS facilitates unified data exchange, remote monitoring, and intelligent automation.

5. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF HUMAN-CENTRIC DIGITAL TWINS

The **Clawdite platform** is designed to be **interoperable, extensible, scalable, and customizable** ensuring **flexibility** in various industrial applications. Its architecture, displayed in *Figure 18*, consists of several key components. **Gateways** serve as standard interfaces for accessing the IIoT Middleware streaming data in predefined formats from devices such as Raspberry Pis, smartphones, tablets, and PLCs. The **IIoT Middleware** enables seamless data flow between components, with support for different middleware integrations based on specific application needs. The **Historical Data Manager (HDM)** retrieves and stores historical data from both Gateways and Functional Modules, addressing a common limitation in middleware solutions like MQTT brokers by enabling advanced reporting and analytics. The **Orchestrator** manages the platform’s overall structure, including Digital Twin instances, worker profiles, installed modules, connected sensors, and message schemas. **Functional Modules** external components that enhance the platform’s capabilities, interact with the Orchestrator and Middleware to process and provide results, further extending the platform’s functionality.

Figure 18 - Clawdite Architecture

This architecture enables efficient and flexible data processing by integrating the data from different sources, parsing and sending this data to end-users or applications in real-time. This setup is crucial for XR5.0, which would require real-time monitoring and data-driven decisions for providing insights about workers behavior and adapting training programs to the user.

5.1 Conceptual Design of Human-centric Digital Twins

The Clawdite reference model *Figure 19* is a framework that integrates human-centered and contextual elements to characterize workers and their production environments. This model supports the creation of extensible, scalable, and adaptable HDTs, offering significant advantages for adopters by providing scientifically robust foundations and ready-to-use packages for instantiating HDTs. These packages include human-centered aspects like interactions and events, as well as software-based simulations and predictions, such as functional models predicting factory entity states.

Key Components of the Clawdite Reference Model

The model organizes data into three main types: **measurements** (dynamic data), **characteristics** (quasi-static data), and **states** (outputs of functional modules), and divides its structure into four groups:

Descriptor Elements:

- Represented by white, red, purple, and blue boxes.
- These elements define quasi-static and static data describing workers and factory entities, including properties, characteristics, measurements, dimensions, and states.
- They serve as the foundation for mapping entities in XR5.0 environments.

Factory Elements:

Represented by yellow boxes.

Describe the hierarchical structure of the factory and its components.

Include dedicated representations of workers to enable data processing in functional modules.

Collect measurements to feed the HDT while adapting the production environment to workers' needs.

Relationship Elements:

- Represented by green and orange boxes.
- Define events, interactions, interventions, and exemptions that describe relationships between factory entities or workers.
- Facilitate orchestration of the production system.

State Elements:

- Represented by sky-blue boxes.
- Functional modules compute insights about factory entities and workers using HDT knowledge.
- Enable simulation, prediction, reasoning, and decision-making capabilities.

5.2 Implementation Framework

5.2.1 Architecture Design and Integration with XR5.0 Architecture

The Clawdite platform architecture introduced at the beginning of this section supports by design the extension into several scenarios. This architecture has been exploited to develop the integration with other components characterizing the XR5.0 architecture.

Figure 20 shows data flows happening in Clawdite when a specific gateway sends metrics about the workers which are collected through dedicated devices. Data enters the platform through Mosquitto IIoT Middleware (MQTT protocol). A specific service (i.e., Historical Data Manager) is in charge of collecting messages exchanged in the IIoT Middleware, ultimately persisting them in the appropriate database. The Orchestrator service allows for platform configurations, such as configuring devices and modelling workers. Data from gateways (collected through the middleware) or from external devices (e.g., cameras) feed the Functional Modules, triggering a new computation based on the specific module purpose. The result of the Functional Module elaboration is sent back to the IIoT Middleware, enabling the gateways to fetch the output of the modules. This worker-related insight from the HDT will be used to optimize specific activities and tasks characterizing the XR5.0 scenario.

Figure 20 - Clawdite Architecture instance for XR5.0

A concrete example of integration based on the described workflow is the worker monitoring use case. A Garmin wearable *device* is used to collect a *measurement* from a *worker* (e.g., the Heart Rate). The measurements are sent to the IIoT Middleware through a dedicated *gateway* (e.g., a smartphone application). These measurements are automatically persisted into the platform, which knows the specifications of the involved entities (i.e., the workers, the devices, the measurements). Persisted data are then available for processing within dedicated Functional Modules and ready to be visualized inside a Grafana dashboard.

Other examples are the two Functional Modules that will be realized for Pilot#1 and Pilot #4, respectively the Workers Movement Prediction and Worker Shadowing modules. In the first one, real-time camera images directly feed the Functional Module, which detects the workers and predicts their short-term movement. The output from the module is sent to the IIoT Middleware and reaches the PLC gateway of the Autonomous Mobile Robot (AMR), which is able to use this information inside its path planning algorithm in order to avoid collisions with humans and optimize the overall AMR movement. In the second example instead, data related to body parts position of the worker (i.e., hands, arms and head) is tracked through the XR device, sent to the IIoT Middleware and saved into the platform. This data is then retrieved by a Functional Module responsible for computing the deviation of the current task execution with respect to an expert technician one (i.e., the shadow). The deviations and ideal execution are sent back to the IIoT Middleware which informs the middleware on the XR device that visualizes these insights.

5.2.2 Clawdite Walkthrough

As part of T3.3, SUPSI developed comprehensive documentation to enable all project participants to effectively use **Clawdite** for their applications and the development of their functional models. The documentation provides detailed guidance on key aspects, including:

- **Getting started with Clawdite:** instructions on setting up and configuring the platform.
- **Core concepts:** explanation of Clawdite’s main components, including data ingestion, processing, and model execution.
- **Application development:** step-by-step tutorials for integrating Clawdite into various use cases.
- **Functional modules development:** guidance on designing and deploying models within the Clawdite environment.

- **Advanced features:** documentation on automation, APIs, and custom extensions for enhanced functionality.

For full details, please refer to the official documentation: [Clawdite How-To Guide](#).

5.3 Functional Modules for HDTs Enrichment

Function Modules serve as independent computing units that form the cognitive layer of the HDTs and enable data processing and analysis functions without compromising the system's modularity. These modules operate as autonomous components that can be integrated into or removed from Clawdite, without compromising the overall functionality of the system. Their design follows a service-oriented approach where each module can retrieve data from multiple sources via the IIoT Middleware.

The modules interact with the system in three main ways: first, they can subscribe to real-time data streams from sensors and other functional modules via the IIoT middleware, allowing them to process continuous streams of information such as physiological data from wearable devices or environmental measurements from the factory floor. Second, they can access static or slowly changing information (e.g. worker profiles, skills or factory layout) via REST APIs provided by the Clawdite platform. Thirdly, they can return their calculation results to the IIoT middleware to make them available to other modules or applications in the ecosystem.

This architectural approach makes it possible to create processing chains in which the modules can build on the results of the other modules. For example, one module could process raw sensor data to recognise workers' activity, while another module uses these activity patterns along with physiological data to assess employee fatigue levels. The modular nature of these components allows end-users and developers to expand their HDT capabilities incrementally, adding new modules as needed. This flexibility is particularly valuable as it allows the HDT to evolve with changing workplace needs and technological capabilities without the need for significant architectural changes.

The ultimate purpose of these functional modules is to transform raw data into meaningful insights about workers and their interactions in the industrial environment and with XR devices, creating a richer and more dynamic digital representation. This enhanced understanding can then be used to optimise

workflows, improve employee well-being and support decision-making processes at various levels of the organisation.

5.3.1 Workers Movement Prediction

Human motion trajectory prediction is a well-explored problem in the literature, spanning various contexts such as pedestrian monitoring in urban traffic, indoor workspaces, construction sites, and Human-Robot Collaboration environments [80]. Regardless of the context, there are three main categories of modeling approaches: physics-based, planning-based, and data-driven/pattern-based. These approaches differ in how they represent and model human motion and its underlying causes. Physics-based methods rely on explicit dynamical models grounded in Newton's laws of motion. Pattern-based methods learn motion patterns from observed agent trajectory data. Planning-based methods focus on reasoning about the motion intent of rational agents [81].

XR5.0 Pilot #1 at KUKA involves the detection and prediction of worker movements in a workspace shared with an Autonomous Mobile Robot, equipped with a 6-axis industrial robot and two RealSense 455 cameras mounted respectively in front and at the back of the AMR, facing opposite directions. The primary objectives are to support optimized path planning for the AMR avoiding the human workers and to facilitate the activation of safety measures (e.g., speed reduction). Moreover, the workers wearing a visor could see the dynamic safety area around the AMR and its planned path.

The Workers Movement Prediction Functional Module is an example of a Clawdite Human Digital Twin extension. The module has a dual focus: detecting the workers position inside a shared dynamic construction environment and predicting workers future movement and positions. The detection step, i.e., identifying humans in the scene and understanding their positions, velocities, head and body orientations, has been addressed by exploiting YOLO-pose [82], a state-of-the-art AI model for pose estimation that continuously elaborates the real time cameras video stream, providing the information needed for computing the required features. In the second step, i.e., predicting workers movement and positions, the features acquired by the detection model feed a prediction model implemented as a Kalman filter [83]: given the worker pose at timestamp t , the model predicts the pose at timestamp $t+1$. The Kalman filter was chosen as an initial approach due to its simplicity and effectiveness in predicting human motion, despite some limitations, such as the potential to predict positions inside obstacles or behind walls. To advance the state-of-the-art model, we incorporated additional features beyond human position and velocity, including body and head orientation. Contextual features may also be beneficial [84]. Future work will explore other methods, such as Markov Decision Process [85], Recurrent Neural Networks/Long Short-Term Memory models [86, 87, 88], Convolutional Neural Networks [89], and Graph-based Neural Networks [80].

This Functional Module will be integrated with Clawdite IIoT Middleware for providing the workers detected position and movement prediction to the AMR gateway, which will be able to use this information in order to optimize the path planning and to activate safety measures. The ultimate goal is to develop an XR-enabled system that can dynamically adjust AMR behavior based on human movement predictions, and to visualize this behaviour inside the workers' visors. A prototype of the Functional Module has been realized and tested in the context of SUPSI's lab, where a setup similar to the KUKA's one has been deployed (i.e., two RealSense D455 cameras installed and configured in the same way). Preliminary tests proved the validity of the prototype, highlighting the need for better orientation detection and improved movement prediction. The case of multiple workers co-existing in the same workspace is a critical challenge to face without using identification techniques due to privacy concerns that require anonymization and legal compliance [90]. Additionally, other limitations are expected to arise when the complete system will be validated inside the dynamic industrial environment, where also the AMR path optimization algorithm (not developed yet) will exploit this information to adjust the AMR routes.

Figure 21 shows an interface built on the Functional Module. On the left hand-side, the interface presents the real-time video streams, collected from the two cameras directly. The human pose detection is performed on the cameras stream and the workers are recognized with a specific $[x, y]$ pixel position and an associated depth. These measures are mapped with a simple algorithm into a 2-dimensional space (i.e.,

the 2D map in the middle), where the detected workers are visualized with red dots. The prediction model computes the estimated movement, which is drawn with a green arrow, and a pink dot is drawn in correspondence of the predicted position, considering a customizable time-window currently fixed at 500 ms. Also, the head and body orientations are detected and drawn with blue and black arrows, respectively. Finally, an occupancy heatmap is shown on the right hand-side which is based on a discrete representation of the workplace. The heatmap highlights the spatial distribution of the workers and it helps in identifying crowded areas.

Figure 21 - Prototype of the Worker Movement Prediction model with a focus on the prediction

5.3.2 Worker Shadowing and Monitoring

XR5.0 Pilot #4 at TAP develops a HDT that emulates the skills of experienced Aircraft Maintenance Technicians (AMTs) (i.e., shadowing task) and continuously monitors new technicians during an aircraft valve maintenance process (i.e., monitoring task). For the maintenance task, the optimal movements of an experienced technician are displayed utilizing XR5.0 visualization while performing the maintenance activity (e.g., the shadow overlay is visible through the visor). On the other hand, for the monitoring task, the HDT provides real-time error feedback and corrections (e.g., by computing the deviation from the optimal maintenance procedure), and tracks performance to assess skill development. By simulating expert techniques and offering real-time guidance, Clawdite enhances training accuracy and consistency in maintenance processes [91], ensuring precise execution and preventing deviations.

The Worker Shadowing and Monitoring Module is another example of Clawdite HDT extension. The main functions of this module are to store and provide the shadow of the expert AMT, and to track, monitor and elaborate feedback about the maintenance process executions. To absolve both these functions, the module uses the movement information (i.e., positions of head and hands) which are tracked directly through the visor. The measurements are filtered for correctly managing noise and outliers, while basic interpolation is performed in order to manage occlusions and temporary tracking errors. The actual maintenance process is matched with the optimal one [92] for computing the deviations over a sliding temporal window based on the task sequence step [93], considering contextual information such as the handedness and skill level of the AMT. If the deviations are higher than a dynamic threshold, which depends on factors such as task duration and complexity, corrective measures are provided to assist the technician in performing the maintenance, along with the shadow overlay of the expert AMT that is always present.

This Functional Module will be integrated with Clawdite IIoT Middleware for providing the expert technician shadow and newbie technician monitoring information to the visor gateway, which will visualize the movements shadow while showing feedback about the actual maintenance process. A first movements

tracking prototype has been realized by IML and deployed as a Meta Store App. The prototype tracks and captures the position and rotation of the user's head and hands, and sends this data via MQTT to the IIoT Middleware at a frequency of 10Hz [94]. This enables Clawdite Platform to read, save and elaborate the data. The app is currently tested by SUPSI on a Meta Quest 2 visor to complete the development and integration of the Functional Module, which will support both Augmented and Virtual Reality environments for enabling mobility and training [95].

More in detail, *Figure 22* is a screenshot of the tracking prototype, which highlights a virtual representation of the user's head and hands, accurately positioned within the environment based on the tracked data. The reference point for the tracking is the origin of the scene in Unity, which corresponds to the starting point of the user. Data is managed via JSON format and contains for each recording the corresponding timestamp along with position and orientation of several identifiers, such as head, right and left hands subparts (e.g., wrist, palm, thumb, index...). Additionally, user profile details such as expertise, handedness, or any other relevant information can be included.

Figure 22 - Prototype of technicians' movement tracking

5.4 Dashboards

Besides Functional Modules, the Clawdite architecture can be extended also through pluggable GUIs, as depicted in Figure 19 and Figure 20. GUIs take several inputs from the Platform but don't produce any output, differently from Functional Module's states, as they are dedicated for visualization purposes only. An example of an integrated GUI is the Grafana Dashboards realized for the worker monitoring use case, where HR data is collected via the UNP application and stored within Clawdite platform. The APIs are not the only way to retrieve such data, in fact Grafana can be directly linked to the platform's InfluxDB where time series are stored, enabling the realization of custom dashboards to visualize measurements information. Two different dashboards have been realized for this use case: Worker monitoring dashboard: it visualizes detailed information related to the Heart Rate of an individual worker, which can be selected inside the dropdown box "workerId" in the top left corner. More in detail, referring to Figure 23, this dashboard shows the historical and current HR values along with minimum, maximum and average values in the selected time window. It computes also the distribution of the HR values, and a chart dedicated to the Workload Intensity, based on the HR value considering following logic:

- Resting (<70 BPM) → ● Low activity (idle or very light work)

- Light effort (70-100 BPM)→🟡 Normal workload (regular, non-strenuous tasks)
- Moderate effort (100-130 BPM)→🟠 Elevated workload (physically demanding tasks)
- High effort (130-150 BPM)→🔴 High strain (intense work, risk of fatigue)
- Overexertion (>150 BPM)→⚫ Critical strain (potential overexertion, risk of fatigue/injury)

These values are derived from various studies in the literature, considering seasonal variations and measurements taken from multiple workers for the resting intervals [96], while the effort intervals are derived from a study focused on work hardness [97].

Figure 24 - Worker Monitoring Dashboard

Cell monitoring dashboard: it visualizes cell-wise information as depicted in Figure 25, assuming that all the workers are assigned to the same work cell. It shows individual or aggregated HR values about each active worker in the selected time window. It visualizes current and historical values for each worker, the current Workload Intensity at a cell-level and the hourly one, which shows the aggregated values for each

hour in the selected time window. Finally there is the alert panel: if the HR value of a worker is higher than 150 BPM, indicating critical strain, an alert is fired and visualized.

Figure 26 - Cell Monitoring Dashboard

Finally, another dashboard has been realized within a different use case: the visualization of measurement information serialized via the UNP AAS application. This application enables to parse, convert and save the information and configuration related to a machine, a PLC or a FactoryEntity in general, translating them in the AAS standard, which could be easily mapped to the Clawdite Data Model. In Figure 27 is depicted the example of a dashboard with data sent from an AAS, corresponding to measurements collected from a Sound Pressure Level sensor. Each measurement represents different types of the sound pressure level readings. The description of each type of measurement is the following:

- LAS values – Level with the A-weighting filter in dB with the slow time constant of 1 second.
- LAS min value – Minimum value of the slow measurement in the current time window.
- LAS max value – Maximum value of the slow measurement in the current time window.
- LAF values – Level with the A-weighting filter in dB with the fast time constant of 0.125 second.
- LAF min value – Minimum value of the fast measurement in the current time window.
- LAF max value – Maximum value of the fast measurement in the current time window.
- LAEq values – Level with the A-weighting filter equivalent continuous, represents the average of sound pressure level (acoustic energy over the time window).

Figure 27 - AAS-Mapped Data Dashboard

5.5 Ethical Considerations

A HDT platform allows detailed virtual representations of workers, enabling optimized resource allocation and enhanced productivity. However, this raises significant legal and ethical concerns, particularly regarding privacy, data security, and human rights [30]. Under GDPR, processing sensitive personal data—such as health information—is strictly regulated and generally prohibited unless specific exceptions, like explicit consent or occupational health requirements, are met. Additionally, the use of such information introduces risks related to workplace surveillance and control, potentially affecting employee well-being, work culture, and motivation. Power imbalances between employers and employees also challenge the validity of consent, as workers may feel pressured to comply.

To mitigate these risks, several strategies are implemented, including worker pseudonymization using UUIDs to decouple data from personal identifiers, transparent consent processes that allow workers to understand and control their data usage, data minimization practices, and robust security measures to protect sensitive information. Additionally, maintaining transparency and involving workers in discussions about monitoring systems can foster trust and promote ethical data usage. These strategies help balance the benefits of workers HR monitoring with safeguarding employee rights and well-being.

5.6 Plan for the Next Period

In the next period, T3.3 will focus on:

- **Realization of Clawdite UI for creating entities and DT exploration:** the development of an intuitive interface within the Clawdite platform will allow users to create and manage digital twin (DT) entities efficiently. This UI will enable users to instantiate new entities, such as workers, sensors and machines, and defining skills, while also providing real-time visualization and interactive exploration of DTs. The UI will support both basic and advanced users by offering guided workflows for creating entities, defining relationships, and configuring data streams. Additionally, visualization tools will be implemented for exploring worker profiles, historical data, and real-time analytics.
- **Workers and Users skills profiling:** this task involves the implementation of a dedicated Functional Module for capturing and analyzing worker skills and competencies over time. The system will integrate data from XR5.0 applications and monitoring tools to assess worker

performance, learning curves, and proficiency levels. The profiling module will categorize workers based on skill sets, experience, and past performance, helping organizations to optimize task assignments, tailor training programs, and improve workforce adaptability. Machine Learning techniques may be explored to detect skill gaps and recommend upskilling opportunities dynamically.

- **Platform multitenancy and HDM refactoring:** the Clawdite platform will be extended to support multi-tenancy, allowing multiple organizations or Pilots to operate within isolated environments while sharing the same XR5.0 instance infrastructure. This will involve implementing role-based access control (RBAC) mechanisms and secure data separation strategies to ensure privacy and data integrity across tenants. Additionally, the Historical Data Manager (HDM) will be refactored to improve its scalability and performance, enhancing its ability to handle large volumes of time-series and structured data efficiently.
- **Completion of Functional Module for Workers Movements Prediction:** the finalization of the module will focus on improving detection and prediction accuracy and robustness for real-world deployment in Pilot #1 at KUKA. Enhancements will include refining human pose estimation techniques using additional contextual cues (e.g., workspace map) and exploring alternative motion prediction models such as Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) or Graph-based Neural Networks. The module will be integrated with the AMR path planning system via Clawdite architecture. Final validation will take place in the Pilot environment to assess performance under real-world conditions.
- **Completion of Functional Module for Workers Shadowing and Monitoring:** the module will be finalized for Pilot #4 at TAP, ensuring that Clawdite accurately represents expert technicians' shadow movements and provides real-time feedback for new trainees. The module will be optimized for performance within Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) environments, with improved tracking algorithms for head and hand positioning. A feedback mechanism will be integrated to compare actual movements against expert benchmarks, dynamically adjusting correction thresholds based on task complexity. The final system will undergo usability testing with technicians to assess effectiveness in training scenarios, with refinements based on user feedback.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The solutions presented in this document and the activities conducted in T3.1, T3.2 and T3.3 create the foundations for the use and integration of the HDT in the XR5.0 project. As we move forward, the next phase will focus on extending the current prototypes in order to reach the expected TRL and prepare them for **piloting activities** in collaboration with XR5.0 industrial partner. These activities will serve as a critical bridge between conceptual development and practical deployment, allowing for iterative improvements based on real-time data and user feedback. These pilot activities will be fundamental in ensuring that the HDT and the related components evolve into a robust, adaptable, and human-centric solution that can support personalised and human-centric XR applications. By systematically testing and validating its capabilities, we aim to create a model that can be extended beyond the initial pilot cases, fostering a **scalable and replicable** approach for digital twin adoption in various industrial domains.

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